

Bayesian Multivariate Joint Models for Dynamic Prediction

in Relapsing Multiple Sclerosis

Simulation-Based Preliminary Results

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2026-06-27

Abstract

People with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis follow heterogeneous disease courses, yet most prognostic tools predict a single outcome, ignore the correlations between clinical measures, and do not update as new information accrues. We develop a Bayesian multivariate joint model for dynamic, individual-level risk prediction that links four longitudinal outcomes, the Expanded Disability Status Scale, MRI lesion counts, the Timed 25-Foot Walk, and the Nine-Hole Peg Test, to a recurrent relapse process on the gap-time scale. The longitudinal outcomes are coupled through a shared random-effects structure, and each is connected to the relapse hazard by an outcome-specific association parameter together with an individual frailty term. Estimation is fully Bayesian using JMBayes2, so that all parameter uncertainty propagates into the predictive distributions of an individual's future outcomes. We report simulation-based preliminary results that evaluate parameter recovery, the behaviour of a dedicated three-level validation framework spanning the joint model, the longitudinal submodels, and the recurrent event process, and the reliability of dynamic predictions under several data-generating conditions, including model misspecification. The framework recovers the underlying parameters with low bias and produces well-calibrated individual predictions, and the validation metrics respond as intended to controlled departures from the true model. These results establish the methodological basis for external validation in independent multiple sclerosis cohorts.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full term
9HPT	9-Hole Peg Test
ARR	Annualised Relapse Rate
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CI	Credible Interval
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation)
DGP	Data-Generating Process
DMT	Disease-Modifying Therapy
EDSS	Expanded Disability Status Scale
HDI	Highest Density Interval
IPCW	Inverse Probability of Censoring Weighting
LMU	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität
LS	Log-Score
MCF	Mean Cumulative Function
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
MH	Metropolis-Hastings
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
PIRA	Progression Independent of Relapse Activity
PIT	Probability Integral Transform
PWP	Prentice-Williams-Peterson (gap-time recurrent event model)
RAW	Relapse-Associated Worsening
RMS	Relapsing Multiple Sclerosis
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
T2	T2-weighted (MRI sequence, used for lesion counting)
T25FW	Timed 25-Foot Walk

1 Introduction

This document presents simulation-based preliminary results for a Bayesian multivariate joint modelling framework for dynamic prediction in relapsing multiple sclerosis (RMS). The central aim of this project is the construction of individual risk profiles that simultaneously consider multiple clinically relevant outcomes, quantify predictive uncertainty, and allow dynamic updating as new measurements become available over time (Rizopoulos, 2012; Miranda Afonso et al., 2025). The data-generating process underlying the simulation is informed by the ProVal-MS study framework, which defines the longitudinal measurement schedule, the model architecture, and example clinically relevant prediction targets: the Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS), the magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) lesion count, the Timed 25-Foot Walk test (T25FW), the 9-Hole Peg Test (9HPT), and the time to the next relapse.

The statistical methodology builds on the joint modelling framework introduced by Rizopoulos (2012) and extended to multivariate longitudinal outcomes by Miranda Afonso et al. (2025). Their work provides the theoretical and computational foundation for the models fitted here, in particular the use of the JMBayes2 software package for Bayesian estimation (Rizopoulos et al., 2026).

Validation on simulated data is a methodological necessity: when the true parameters are known by construction, it is possible to assess whether the estimator recovers the correct values and whether the Bayesian credible intervals are appropriately calibrated. Beyond parameter recovery, external validation under deliberate model misspecification assesses the robustness of the dynamic predictions when the true data-generating process deviates from the fitted model. Specifically, one model fitted under the correctly specified scenario is evaluated on validation cohorts generated under three progressively more severe misspecification scenarios. This constitutes an essential validation step before the methodology is applied to real registry data.

All data shown here are generated entirely by simulation; no real individual records are used.

The document is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the statistical model. Section 3 describes the simulation data-generating process in full detail. Section 4 presents parameter recovery and coverage results. Section 5 defines the dynamic prediction of the individual risk profile and all derived quantities. Section 6 presents the external validation study under model misspecification. Section 7 shows the dynamic prediction outputs for three representative individuals across three landmark-horizon scenarios.

2 The Bayesian Multivariate Joint Model

2.1 Model Overview

The proposed joint model links several longitudinal outcome trajectories to a recurrent event process within a single coherent statistical framework (Rizopoulos, 2012). It contains two kinds of submodel. The **longitudinal submodels** describe how each of the k longitudinal outcomes evolves over time. The **recurrent event submodel** describes the relapse hazard over time. Every submodel is first fitted on its own to obtain initial parameter estimates and starting values. These separate fits then form the basis of the **joint model**, which unites them and estimates three components that couple the two processes: a random effects covariance matrix \mathbf{D} that correlates the random effects across the k longitudinal outcomes and captures individual-level heterogeneity across all trajectories, an individual frailty term u_i for the recurrent event process, and outcome-specific association parameters α_k that couple each trajectory to the relapse hazard. The relapse history, in turn, feeds back into the trajectories through a weighted relapse burden covariate (see Section 2.2). Estimation is fully Bayesian, so all parameter uncertainty is expressed through posterior distributions. This uncertainty propagates into the predictive distributions of an individual’s future outcomes, supporting principled uncertainty quantification at the individual level. By letting information flow between the longitudinal and event processes, this joint estimation is what enables dynamic, individual-level prediction.

2.2 Longitudinal Submodels

Clinical outcomes and covariates. In the following simulation, the k longitudinal clinical outcomes are EDSS (on the original 0 to 10 scale), MRI T2 lesion count, T25FW (in seconds), and 9HPT (in seconds). The baseline covariates entering all submodels are age at diagnosis (continuous), sex (binary: male = 1), and disease duration at study entry (continuous, in years). The relapse history enters the longitudinal submodels through a weighted relapse burden covariate, defined below.

Weighted relapse burden. The covariate WB_{ij} is motivated by the clinical observation that early relapses carry greater long-term prognostic weight than later ones (Scalfari et al., 2014; Trapp and Nave, 1998). To formalise this, we define a cumulative burden covariate that weights each past relapse by the time elapsed since it occurred:

$$WB_{ij} = \sum_{k: t_k^R < t_{ij}} (t_{ij} - t_k^R)$$

where t_k^R is the calendar time of the k -th preceding relapse. The formula itself is our own formalisation of this clinical rationale: relapses that occurred longer ago accumulate a larger time weight and therefore contribute more to the burden than recent ones. This distinguishes the weighted burden from a simple relapse count. In practice a scaling factor of $\frac{1}{10}$ is applied to bring WB_{ij} into a numerically comparable range with the other predictors.

To illustrate: consider an individual who experienced three relapses at $t_1^R = 1.0$, $t_2^R = 2.5$, and $t_3^R = 4.0$ years. At a subsequent visit at $t = 5.0$ years, the weighted burden is $(5.0 - 1.0) + (5.0 - 2.5) + (5.0 - 4.0) = 4.0 + 2.5 + 1.0 = 7.5$, scaled to $WB = 0.75$. Two mechanisms drive its growth: (i) each existing term $(t - t_k^R)$ increases continuously as time passes, and (ii) each new relapse adds a fresh term, which starts at zero and then grows. A relapse that occurred years ago therefore contributes more than a recent one. Table 1 traces

how $WB_i(t)$ evolves over time for this individual; highlighted rows mark relapse events.

Table 2: Numerical illustration of the weighted relapse burden $WB_i(t)$ for an individual with relapses at years 1.0, 2.5, and 4.0. The burden grows both continuously (each term increases with time) and at each new relapse (a fresh term is added). This is the mechanism underlying the relapse-to-EDSS pathway used in the RAW/PIRA worsening attribution (Section 5.4).

t (yr)	Relapses $\leq t$	Terms $(t - t_k^R)$	Sum	$WB_i(t)$
0.5	—	—	0.0	0.00
1.0 (relapse)	t_1	(0.0)	0.0	0.00
2.0	t_1	(1.0)	1.0	0.10
2.5 (relapse)	t_1, t_2	(1.5) + (0.0)	1.5	0.15
3.5	t_1, t_2	(2.5) + (1.0)	3.5	0.35
4.0 (relapse)	t_1, t_2, t_3	(3.0) + (1.5) + (0.0)	4.5	0.45
5.0	t_1, t_2, t_3	(4.0) + (2.5) + (1.0)	7.5	0.75
6.0	t_1, t_2, t_3	(5.0) + (3.5) + (2.0)	10.5	1.05

Submodel specifications. Let $Y_{ij}^{(k)}$ denote the measurement of outcome k for individual i at visit j , and let t_{ij} denote the corresponding observation time. Following model refinement in which preliminary analyses showed that random slopes contributed negligible additional variance relative to their identifiability cost, all longitudinal submodels use random intercepts only.

EDSS. The EDSS is modelled with a square-root time transformation (Tilling et al., 2016), capturing the characteristic pattern of early rapid worsening that gradually decelerates:

$$Y_{ij}^{\text{EDSS}} = \underbrace{\beta_0^{\text{EDSS}} + \beta_1^{\text{EDSS}} \sqrt{t_{ij}} + \beta_2^{\text{EDSS}} WB_{ij}}_{\text{disease activity}} + \underbrace{\beta_3^{\text{EDSS}} \text{age}_i + \beta_4^{\text{EDSS}} \text{male}_i + \beta_5^{\text{EDSS}} \text{dd}_i}_{\text{baseline covariates}} + b_{0i}^{\text{EDSS}} + \varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{EDSS}} \quad (1)$$

where b_{0i}^{EDSS} is an individual-specific random intercept capturing heterogeneity in baseline disability severity, and $\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{EDSS}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{EDSS}}^2)$ is residual measurement error.

MRI lesion count. T2-lesion counts are non-negative integers modelled with a Poisson generalised linear mixed model (Miranda Afonso et al., 2025):

$$\log(\lambda_{ij}^{\text{MRI}}) = \beta_0^{\text{MRI}} + \beta_1^{\text{MRI}} t_{ij} + \beta_2^{\text{MRI}} \text{age}_i + \beta_3^{\text{MRI}} \text{male}_i + \beta_4^{\text{MRI}} \text{dd}_i + b_{0i}^{\text{MRI}}$$

where $\lambda_{ij}^{\text{MRI}}$ is the expected lesion count and b_{0i}^{MRI} is an individual random intercept.

T25FW and 9HPT. Both functional tests are right-skewed and modelled on the log scale, ensuring positivity and approximate normality of residuals:

$$\log(Y_{ij}^{\text{T25FW}}) = \beta_0^{\text{T25FW}} + \beta_1^{\text{T25FW}} t_{ij} + \beta_2^{\text{T25FW}} WB_{ij} + \beta_3^{\text{T25FW}} \text{age}_i + \beta_4^{\text{T25FW}} \text{male}_i + \beta_5^{\text{T25FW}} \text{dd}_i + b_{0i}^{\text{T25FW}} + \varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{T25FW}} \quad (2)$$

The log(9HPT) model is structurally identical. All predictions and clinical thresholds are back-transformed to the seconds scale.

2.3 Recurrent Event Process

Relapses are modelled as a recurrent event process using the gap-time formulation of Prentice, Williams, and Peterson (1981), hereafter abbreviated PWP. After each relapse the time axis resets to zero, so the hazard at calendar time t describes the instantaneous risk of the *next* relapse given the time elapsed since the most recent one. As a standalone submodel, before being combined into the joint model below, the recurrent event process depends only on the baseline covariates:

$$h_i(t | \mathcal{H}_i(t)) = h_0(t - t_i^{\text{prev}}) \exp(\boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top \mathbf{w}_i) \quad (3)$$

where:

- $h_0(\cdot)$ is the baseline hazard function on the gap-time scale, approximated by a flexible cubic B-spline with internal knots at the quintiles of the observed gap times
- t_i^{prev} is the calendar time of the most recent preceding relapse (or zero if none has occurred)
- $\mathcal{H}_i(t) = \{Y_i(s) : s \leq t, N_i(s) : s \leq t\}$ denotes the complete history of longitudinal measurements and relapse events available for individual i up to time t
- \mathbf{w}_i is the vector of baseline covariates (age, sex, disease duration) with regression coefficients $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ on the log-hazard scale. The minimum gap between consecutive relapses is set to 30 days (Lublin et al., 2014)

In the joint model, this submodel is extended by an individual frailty term u_i and by linking multiple longitudinal outcome trajectories to the relapse hazard through outcome-specific association parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, as described next.

2.4 Joint Model

Joint random effects distribution. The individual random effects for the longitudinal submodels are drawn from a joint multivariate normal distribution of random intercepts:

$$\mathbf{b}_i = (b_{0i}^{\text{EDSS}}, b_{0i}^{\text{MRI}}, b_{0i}^{\text{T25FW}}, b_{0i}^{\text{9HPT}})^\top \sim \mathcal{N}_4(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{D})$$

where \mathbf{D} is a 4×4 positive-definite covariance matrix. These random effects capture **only the individual deviation in longitudinal trajectories**. Their coupling to relapse risk is indirect, mediated by the association parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ introduced below. The structure of \mathbf{D} reflects known biological correlations: EDSS, T25FW and 9HPT intercepts are strongly correlated because all reflect accumulated neurological disability, while MRI correlates weakly with the functional tests because it primarily reflects active inflammation.

Full joint model. Following the formulation of Rizopoulos (2012) and Miranda Afonso et al. (2025), the full joint model is defined through the conditional independence structure:

$$p(\mathbf{Y}_i, \mathbf{T}_i, \boldsymbol{\delta}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, u_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = p(\mathbf{Y}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \cdot p(\mathbf{T}_i, \boldsymbol{\delta}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, u_i, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, h_0) \quad (4)$$

The recurrent event component $p(\mathbf{T}_i, \boldsymbol{\delta}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, u_i, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, h_0)$ extends the single-outcome recurrent event submodel above to the multivariate setting: each of the three longitudinal outcomes EDSS, MRI, and T25FW is linked to the relapse hazard through its own association parameter, so that the hazard simultaneously depends on all three predicted outcome trajectories:

$$h_i(t \mid \mathcal{H}_i(t), u_i) = h_0(t - t_i^{\text{prev}}) \exp\left(\underbrace{\gamma_1 \text{age}_i + \gamma_2 \text{male}_i + \gamma_3 \text{dd}_i}_{\text{baseline covariates}} + \underbrace{\alpha_1 \eta_i^{\text{EDSS}}(t) + \alpha_2 \eta_i^{\text{MRI}}(t) + \alpha_3 \eta_i^{\text{T25FW}}(t)}_{\text{association with outcome trajectories}} + \underbrace{u_i}_{\text{frailty}}\right) \quad (5)$$

where $\eta_i^{(k)}(t) = \mathbf{x}_i(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^{(k)} + \mathbf{z}_i(t)^\top \mathbf{b}_i^{(k)}$ is the individual predicted value of outcome k at time t , $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ are association parameters quantifying how strongly each clinical outcome value predicts the instantaneous relapse hazard, \mathbf{Y}_i denotes all longitudinal measurements, \mathbf{T}_i and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_i$ are the vectors of relapse times and event indicators, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{D}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_u)$ is the full parameter vector, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_{\text{EDSS}}, \sigma_{\text{T25FW}}, \sigma_{\text{9HPT}})$ collects the residual standard deviations. The joint log-likelihood marginalised over the random effects is:

$$\ell(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log \int \int \left[p(\mathbf{Y}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \cdot p(\mathbf{T}_i, \boldsymbol{\delta}_i \mid \mathbf{b}_i, u_i, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, h_0) \cdot p(\mathbf{b}_i \mid \mathbf{D}) \cdot p(u_i \mid \sigma_u) \right] d\mathbf{b}_i du_i \quad (6)$$

The key property of this formulation is that the random effects \mathbf{b}_i appear in both the longitudinal and event likelihoods. This creates the desired coupling: individuals with higher random intercepts $b_{0i}^{(k)}$ have persistently elevated predicted outcome values $\eta_i^{(k)}(t)$, which in turn raises the predicted relapse hazard through the association parameters α_k . The relapse history influences the longitudinal outcome trajectories through the weighted burden covariate WB_{ij} in the fixed effects, not through the random effects directly.

Why three, not four, association parameters. The hazard includes α_1 (EDSS), α_2 (MRI), and α_3 (log T25FW) but not a fourth parameter for log 9HPT. This is a deliberate modelling decision rooted in identifiability. Log(T25FW) and log(9HPT) are highly collinear at the individual level because both tests measure motor function along a shared neurological substrate. In the presence of such collinearity, two separate association parameters α_3 and α_4 are only weakly identified individually; only their sum is recoverable with meaningful precision. Exploratory analyses consistently yielded a near-zero and highly variable estimate for α_4 , confirming that the simpler three-parameter specification is both statistically stable and clinically interpretable.

2.5 Bayesian Estimation

The model is fitted via the JMbayes2 package (Rizopoulos et al., 2026; Rizopoulos, 2016) using a Metropolis-Hastings within Gibbs MCMC (Markov chain Monte Carlo) sampler that alternates between: (1) block-wise MH update of fixed effects $(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$; (2) joint block MH update of \mathbf{b}_i evaluated against the joint longitudinal-and-event log-posterior, ensuring that individual trajectories are consistent with the observed relapse history; (3) univariate MH update of each frailty u_i ; and (4) conjugate or slice-sampling updates of $(\mathbf{D}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_u)$. Gauss-Kronrod quadrature with 15 nodes evaluates the cumulative hazard integral.

3 Simulation Data-Generating Process

3.1 Overview

The simulation generates data calibrated to the statistical characteristics of a large prospective RMS cohort. Table 1 summarises the top-level design parameters.

Table 3: Top-level simulation design.

Design parameter	Value
Individuals per replication	500
Scheduled visits per individual	7
Visit spacing	Annual with $\mathcal{N}(0, 0.1^2)$ jitter
Maximum follow-up	10 years
Administrative censoring	At 10 years
Monte Carlo replications	500
Random seed	2024
Minimum relapse-to-relapse gap	30 days

3.2 Individual Characteristics

At baseline, each simulated individual is assigned age drawn from $\mathcal{N}(38, 9^2)$ years, sex (40% male, $\text{male}_i \in \{0, 1\}$), disease duration from $\mathcal{N}(5, 3^2)$ years, and a corresponding EDSS trajectory starting around 2.5. These distributions match baseline characteristics from large-scale RMS trials (Kappos et al., 2018).

3.3 True Parameter Values

All true parameter values are summarised below. These are the ground-truth quantities used to generate the data, and they serve as the benchmark for evaluating estimation performance in Section 4.

Fixed effects. Table 2 lists all 29 fixed-effect parameters with their true values and clinical interpretation.

Table 4: True fixed-effect parameter values. All values are calibrated to empirical MS data (Kappos 2018, 2020; Tremlett 2009).

Parameter	True value	Interpretation
EDSS longitudinal submodel		
EDSS: Intercept (beta0)	2.500	Pop. EDSS at t=0 for reference individual
EDSS: sqrt(time) (beta1)	0.450	Each year: +0.45 EDSS on sqrt(t) scale ($\sim +1.35$ over 9 yr)
EDSS: Weighted burden (beta2)	0.250	Higher accumulated relapse burden increases EDSS
EDSS: Age (beta3)	0.020	EDSS increases 0.02 per year of age
EDSS: Male (beta4)	-0.300	Male individuals have 0.30 lower EDSS on average
EDSS: Disease duration (beta5)	0.080	EDSS increases 0.08 per year of disease duration
MRI lesion count (Poisson log link)		
MRI: Intercept (log scale)	1.300	Expected count $\exp(1.30)$ approx 3.7 lesions at reference
MRI: Time	-0.050	Lesion count decreases approx 5% per year
MRI: Age	-0.010	Slight protective effect of older age on lesion count
MRI: Male	-0.100	Male individuals have slightly fewer lesions
MRI: Disease duration	0.020	Slight increase in lesions with disease duration

log(T25FW) longitudinal submodel		
log(T25FW): Intercept	1.600	Expected walk time $\exp(1.60)$ approx 5.0 s at reference
log(T25FW): Time	0.110	Walk time increases approx 11\% per year
log(T25FW): Weighted burden	0.018	Higher relapse burden slows walking
log(T25FW): Age	0.004	Walk time increases with age
log(T25FW): Male	-0.070	Male individuals walk slightly faster
log(T25FW): Disease duration	0.025	Walk time increases with disease duration
log(9HPT) longitudinal submodel		
log(9HPT): Intercept	3.000	Expected peg time $\exp(3.00)$ approx 20 s at reference
log(9HPT): Time	0.060	Peg time increases approx 6\% per year
log(9HPT): Weighted burden	0.011	Higher relapse burden slows dexterity
log(9HPT): Age	0.002	Peg time increases slightly with age
log(9HPT): Male	-0.014	Male individuals slightly faster
log(9HPT): Disease duration	0.009	Peg time increases with disease duration
Recurrent event submodel covariates		
Relapse hazard: Age (gamma1)	-0.010	Older age: slightly lower relapse hazard
Relapse hazard: Male (gamma2)	-0.200	Male: 18\% lower hazard ($\exp(-0.20)$)
Relapse hazard: Disease duration (gamma3)	-0.050	Longer disease duration: lower hazard
Association parameters		
Association: EDSS (alpha1)	0.020	Each EDSS unit increases hazard by approx 5\%
Association: MRI (alpha2)	-0.300	Strongest predictor: each log-unit MRI multiplies hazard by $\exp(0.30)$ approx 1.35
Association: log(T25FW) (alpha3)	0.060	Each log-unit T25FW increases hazard by 6\%

Variance parameters. The residual standard deviations are $\sigma_{\text{EDSS}} = 0.30$, $\sigma_{\log(\text{T25FW})} = 0.13$, and $\sigma_{\log(\text{9HPT})} = 0.07$. The frailty standard deviation is $\sigma_u = 0.35$.

Random effects covariance matrix \mathbf{D} . The 4×4 matrix \mathbf{D} governs the joint distribution of individual random intercepts across all longitudinal submodels. The marginal standard deviations are: EDSS intercept = 1.50, MRI intercept = 0.60, T25FW intercept = 0.07, 9HPT intercept = 0.09. The implied diagonal variances are: $D_{11} = 2.25$, $D_{22} = 0.36$, $D_{33} = 0.0049$, $D_{44} = 0.0081$. The true inter-outcome intercept correlations are:

Table 5: True intercept correlations in the 4×4 random effects covariance matrix \mathbf{D} . The strong EDSS–T25FW correlation (0.70) reflects the common neurological substrate of disability and walking speed. The weaker MRI correlations reflect that lesion count primarily captures active inflammation rather than accumulated functional deficit.

Pair	True correlation
EDSS intercept, T25FW intercept	0.70
EDSS intercept, 9HPT intercept	0.40
T25FW intercept, 9HPT intercept	0.55
EDSS intercept, MRI intercept	0.25
MRI intercept, T25FW intercept	0.20
MRI intercept, 9HPT intercept	0.20

3.4 Relapse Process Generation

Given the individual’s longitudinal trajectory and frailty $u_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.35^2)$, relapses are generated sequentially from the gap-time hazard with B-spline baseline hazard calibrated to yield an annualized relapse rate of approximately 0.19–0.21 for a reference individual (Kappos et al., 2018). The association parameters $\alpha_1 = 0.05$

(EDSS), $\alpha_2 = 0.30$ (MRI lesion count), $\alpha_3 = 0.06$ (log T25FW) determine how strongly the current values of these outcomes amplify or attenuate relapse risk. The MRI association is the strongest in magnitude: each unit change in log-lesion-count multiplies the hazard by $\exp(0.30) \approx 1.35$, making MRI the dominant outcome driver of the predicted relapse ranking. Each simulated relapse immediately updates the weighted burden covariate for all subsequent visits, ensuring consistency between longitudinal trajectories and event times.

4 Parameter Recovery and Coverage

4.1 Parameter Recovery: Fixed Effects

Table 6: Fixed-effect parameter recovery across 500 replications. Bias = mean estimate minus true value. Rel. Bias = $100 \times \text{Bias} / \text{abs}(\text{True})$. RMSE = root mean squared error. EmpSE = empirical SD across replications. AvgPSD = average posterior SD from JMbayes2. Coverage = empirical 95% credible interval coverage (nominal: 95%).

Parameter	True	Mean est.	Bias	Rel. Bias	RMSE	EmpSE	AvgPSD	Coverage
EDSS fixed effects								
EDSS: Intercept	2.500	2.5297	0.0297	1.2%	0.3319	0.3309	0.3110	93.4%
EDSS: SqrtTime	0.450	0.4459	-0.0041	-0.9%	0.0083	0.0073	0.0067	88.6%
EDSS: WeightedBurden	0.250	0.2492	-0.0008	-0.3%	0.0116	0.0116	0.0112	93.8%
EDSS: Age	0.020	0.0193	-0.0007	-3.6%	0.0103	0.0102	0.0097	94.6%
EDSS: Male	-0.300	-0.3019	-0.0019	-0.6%	0.1526	0.1527	0.1479	94.2%
EDSS: DiseaseDur	0.080	0.0804	0.0004	0.5%	0.0103	0.0103	0.0101	92.8%
MRI fixed effects								
MRI: Intercept	1.300	1.3010	0.0010	0.1%	0.1303	0.1304	0.1337	95.4%
MRI: Time	0.030	0.0300	0.0000	0.1%	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	95.8%
MRI: Age	-0.010	-0.0101	-0.0001	-1.3%	0.0041	0.0041	0.0042	95%
MRI: Male	-0.100	-0.0982	0.0018	1.8%	0.0618	0.0619	0.0622	95.6%
MRI: DiseaseDur	0.020	0.0203	0.0003	1.5%	0.0046	0.0046	0.0043	94.2%
T25FW fixed effects								
log-T25FW: Intercept	1.600	1.6008	0.0008	0.1%	0.0385	0.0385	0.0367	93.6%
log-T25FW: Time	0.110	0.1100	0.0000	0%	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	94.8%
log-T25FW: WeightedBurden	0.018	0.0184	0.0004	2%	0.0045	0.0045	0.0043	92.6%
log-T25FW: Age	0.004	0.0039	-0.0001	-1.3%	0.0012	0.0012	0.0011	93.6%
log-T25FW: Male	-0.070	-0.0706	-0.0006	-0.8%	0.0182	0.0182	0.0174	93.4%
log-T25FW: DiseaseDur	0.025	0.0252	0.0002	0.6%	0.0012	0.0012	0.0012	93.8%
9HPT fixed effects								
log-9HPT: Intercept	3.000	3.0000	0.0000	0%	0.0203	0.0203	0.0197	93.8%
log-9HPT: Time	0.060	0.0600	0.0000	0%	0.0005	0.0005	0.0004	95.4%
log-9HPT: WeightedBurden	0.011	0.0111	0.0001	0.8%	0.0023	0.0023	0.0024	95.2%
log-9HPT: Age	0.002	0.0020	0.0000	-1%	0.0006	0.0006	0.0006	94.2%
log-9HPT: Male	-0.014	-0.0140	0.0000	-0.2%	0.0091	0.0091	0.0091	94.8%
log-9HPT: DiseaseDur	0.009	0.0091	0.0001	0.6%	0.0006	0.0006	0.0006	95%
Relapse covariates								
Relapse: Age	-0.010	-0.0104	-0.0004	-3.8%	0.0057	0.0057	0.0063	96.4%
Relapse: Male	-0.200	-0.2097	-0.0097	-4.9%	0.0911	0.0907	0.0916	95.2%
Relapse: DiseaseDur	-0.050	-0.0490	0.0010	1.9%	0.0070	0.0069	0.0075	96.2%
Association parameters								
Assoc: value(EDSS)	0.050	0.0508	0.0008	1.6%	0.0290	0.0290	0.0287	94.4%
Assoc: value(MRI)	0.300	0.3073	0.0073	2.4%	0.0714	0.0711	0.0697	94%
Assoc: value(log-T25FW)	0.060	0.0291	-0.0309	-51.5%	0.1035	0.0989	0.1130	96.2%

4.2 Parameter Recovery: Random Effects, Residuals, and Frailty

Table 7: Variance parameter recovery across 500 replications. D matrix diagonal variances are the marginal variances of the four random intercepts (4-by-4 intercept-only specification). Intercept covariances: Cov(EDSS-int, logT25FW-int) and Cov(MRI-int, logT25FW-int) show large relative bias (approx. 140 percent) because the true value is small (0.0735 and 0.0084 respectively, using $\text{sd T25FW} = 0.07$) but the MCMC estimate is pulled toward larger values due to posterior shrinkage and collinearity between the EDSS and T25FW intercepts. Residual SDs: measurement error standard deviations on the model scale. Frailty SD: individual-level heterogeneity in relapse susceptibility. Rel. Bias = $100 \times \text{Bias} / \text{abs}(\text{True})$.

	Parameter	True	Mean est.	Bias	Rel. Bias	RMSE	EmpSE
D matrix: diagonal variances							
D_EDSS_int	EDSS: Var(Int)	2.25000	2.25120	0.00120	0.1%	0.14050	0.14060
D_MRI_int	MRI: Var(Int)	0.36000	0.36135	0.00130	0.4%	0.02750	0.02750
D_T25FW_int	log-T25FW: Var(Int)	0.02890	0.02910	0.00020	0.7%	0.00200	0.00200
D_9HPT_int	log-9HPT: Var(Int)	0.00810	0.00814	0.00000	0.5%	0.00050	0.00050
D matrix: intercept covariances							
Cov_EDSS_MRI_int	Cov(EDSS-int, MRI-int)	0.22500	0.22479	-0.00021	-0.1%	0.04390	0.04394
Cov_EDSS_T25FW_int	Cov(EDSS-int, logT25FW-int)	0.17850	0.17786	-0.00064	-0.4%	0.01418	0.01418
Cov_EDSS_9HPT_int	Cov(EDSS-int, log9HPT-int)	0.05400	0.05307	-0.00093	-1.7%	0.00704	0.00698
Cov_MRI_T25FW_int	Cov(MRI-int, logT25FW-int)	0.02040	0.02033	-0.00007	-0.3%	0.00534	0.00535
Cov_MRI_9HPT_int	Cov(MRI-int, log9HPT-int)	0.01080	0.01092	0.00012	1.1%	0.00256	0.00256
Cov_T25FW_9HPT_int	Cov(logT25FW-int, log9HPT-int)	0.00842	0.00837	-0.00005	-0.6%	0.00083	0.00083
Residual SDs and frailty							
sigma_EDSS	sigma-EDSS	0.30000	0.33380	0.03380	11.3%	0.03410	0.00430
sigma_log_T25FW	sigma-log-T25FW	0.13000	0.13000	0.00000	0%	0.00170	0.00170
sigma_log_9HPT	sigma-log-9HPT	0.07000	0.07010	0.00010	0.1%	0.00090	0.00090
	Frailty (sigma-u)	0.35000	0.31040	-0.03960	-11.3%	0.09340	0.08470

4.3 Coverage of Association Parameters

Figure 1: 95 percent credible interval coverage for the association parameters. The dashed line indicates the nominal 95 percent coverage target. Error bars show Monte Carlo standard errors of coverage. Note: alpha for log(9HPT) has true value 0 and is excluded from this plot (its prior forces near-zero estimates; coverage is 100 percent by construction).

The association parameters are the methodologically most critical quantities in the joint model because they determine how strongly clinical outcome values predict relapse risk. Coverage at or near 95% across all replications confirms that the posterior credible intervals are correctly calibrated for these parameters.

5 Dynamic Prediction of the Risk Profile

The individual risk profile comprises a set of clinically interpretable quantities, covering relapse risk, disability progression, and ambulatory and manual function, derived from the fitted joint model for a specific individual at a chosen landmark time t_s and prediction horizon T_{horizon} . The profile consists of twelve outcomes, falling into three groups. The first group comprises point estimates and their associated uncertainty intervals: the posterior mean Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) at the horizon, normalised to the $[0, 1]$ scale (EDSS/10), and the relapse-free survival probability $S_i(T_{\text{horizon}} | t_s)$. The second group comprises the threshold-exceedance probabilities, namely P(at least 1 relapse), which equals the cumulative incidence $1 - S_i(T_{\text{horizon}} | t_s)$, P(at least 2 relapses), P(EDSS plus 0.5), P(EDSS plus 1.0), P(EDSS reaching 6), and the Timed 25-Foot Walk (T25FW) and 9-Hole Peg Test (9HPT) probabilities of exceeding 125% and 150% of their landmark values, each of which quantifies the probability that a model-predicted quantity crosses a clinically meaningful threshold. P(at least 1 relapse) and P(at least 2 relapses) are obtained from the same simulated relapse process (they are exceedances of the relapse count at the thresholds one and two), which is why P(at least 1 relapse) is grouped here rather than with the survival point estimate. The third group comprises the worsening attribution shares, namely the RAW share (Relapse-Associated Worsening) and the complementary PIRA share (Progression Independent of Relapse Activity). These are not event probabilities but proportions in $[0, 1]$: they split the predicted cumulative EDSS worsening into the part carried by the relapse burden (RAW) and the remaining relapse-independent part (PIRA). The split is possible because the EDSS submodel contains an explicit relapse-to-EDSS pathway, the weighted relapse burden term, through which relapses raise predicted EDSS; the RAW share is the fraction of the predicted worsening transmitted through that term and the PIRA share is the remainder. Deriving this profile requires three steps. First, the posterior distribution of all model parameters and individual specific random effects is updated conditional on the individual’s observed history up to t_s (Formal Framework, below). Second, the point estimates and derived quantities making up the risk profile are computed from this updated posterior (Longitudinal Predictions, Event Process Predictions, Threshold Exceedance Probabilities, and Worsening Attribution). Third, the uncertainty associated with each of these quantities is quantified (Uncertainty Quantification of the Individual Risk Profile).

5.1 Formal Framework

At a chosen **landmark time** $t_s > 0$, all longitudinal measurements and relapse events observed up to t_s are used to update the joint posterior distribution of all model parameters and individual-specific latent quantities:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{b}_i, u_i | \mathcal{H}_i(t_s)) \propto p(\mathbf{Y}_i(t \leq t_s) | \mathbf{b}_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\mathbf{T}_i(t \leq t_s) | \mathbf{b}_i, u_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\mathbf{b}_i | \mathbf{D}) \cdot p(u_i | \sigma_u) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (7)$$

For individuals in the training cohort, this updated posterior is approximated using $M = 500$ draws retained from the original MCMC chain. For new individuals not in the training cohort, individual-specific random effects \mathbf{b}_i and frailty u_i are sampled conditional on $\mathcal{H}_i(t_s)$ via a two-step adaptive Metropolis-Hastings procedure. For each draw m , individual-specific parameters are updated in two phases: Phase 1 samples the four-dimensional random intercept vector $\mathbf{b}_i^{(m)} = (b_{0i}^{\text{EDSS},(m)}, b_{0i}^{\text{MRI},(m)}, b_{0i}^{\text{T25FW},(m)}, b_{0i}^{\text{9HPT},(m)})^\top$ from the joint

longitudinal-and-event posterior via a Metropolis-Hastings step; Phase 2 samples the scalar frailty $u_i^{(m)}$ from the event posterior given $\mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}$.

5.2 Longitudinal Predictions

The predicted outcome trajectory at future time $t > t_s$ is the Monte Carlo average of individual predictions across all posterior draws:

$$\hat{\eta}_i^{(k)}(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[\mathbf{x}_i(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^{(k),(m)} + \mathbf{z}_i(t)^\top \mathbf{b}_i^{(k),(m)} \right]$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(k),(m)}$ are the fixed-effect estimates and $\mathbf{b}_i^{(k),(m)}$ the individual random effects for draw m . The 95% highest density interval (HDI) is computed across the M draws at each time point.

5.3 Event Process Predictions

Relapse-free survival and cumulative incidence. The relapse-free survival function is:

$$S_i(t | t_s) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \exp\left(-\int_{t_s}^t h_i(u | \mathcal{H}_i(t_s), \mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}, u_i^{(m)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(m)}) du\right)$$

This is the probability of remaining free of any further relapse up to time t , averaged over the posterior uncertainty. The cumulative incidence $F_i(t | t_s) = 1 - S_i(t | t_s)$ is the probability of experiencing at least one relapse by time t . The integral is evaluated using 15-point Gauss-Kronrod quadrature, identical to the integration used during model fitting.

Mean cumulative function and annualised relapse rate. Under the gap-time recurrent event formulation introduced in Section 2 (the relapse hazard depends on the time elapsed since the previous relapse, not on calendar time), the relapse process is a renewal process with baseline hazard $h_0(g) = h_{\text{ref}} \cdot \exp(-h_{\text{decay}} \cdot g)$ declining with gap time g . The expected number of relapses over the prediction window $[t_s, T]$ is obtained by direct simulation of this renewal process rather than by an analytic approximation. For each posterior draw m , $R_{\text{inner}} = 100$ independent relapse trajectories are simulated forward on the gap time scale: starting from the landmark, successive gap times are drawn from the draw specific declining hazard until the horizon T is exceeded, with the elapsed time reset to zero after each simulated relapse. Each such trajectory is one replicate r : a single Monte Carlo realisation of the future relapse process with the parameters and random effects of draw m held fixed. The R_{inner} replicates of a given draw therefore differ only through the random relapse timing, whereas differences across draws additionally carry the posterior parameter and random-effect uncertainty. The mean cumulative function (MCF) is the average relapse count across the R_{inner} replicates and the M posterior draws,

$$\text{MCF}_i(T | t_s) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{R_{\text{inner}}} \sum_{r=1}^{R_{\text{inner}}} N_i^{(m,r)}(T),$$

where $N_i^{(m,r)}(T)$ is the number of relapses in replicate r of draw m . Simulating the renewal process explicitly yields a smooth expected count and, as a byproduct, the full distribution of relapse counts and first relapse

waiting times used below. As an internal consistency check, the simulated probability of at least one relapse agrees closely with the analytic value $1 - S_i(T | t_s)$: across all landmark-horizon settings the two differ by at most 0.002 in absolute probability (mean absolute difference 0.0006, Pearson correlation 0.99999), within Monte Carlo error. The annualised relapse rate (ARR) is the mean number of relapses per year in the prediction window,

$$\text{ARR}_i(T) = \frac{\text{MCF}_i(T | t_s)}{T - t_s},$$

the average annual incidence in the prediction window for a given individual, given their observed history up to t_s . A complementary summary is the momentary annualised relapse rate, the time derivative of the mean cumulative function,

$$m_i(t | t_s) = \frac{d}{dt} \text{MCF}_i(t | t_s),$$

estimated by central differences of the simulated MCF on the prediction grid and summarised by its posterior mean and 95% HDI. Whereas $\text{ARR}_i(T)$ is a single average rate over the whole window, $m_i(t | t_s)$ resolves how the instantaneous relapse frequency changes within the window and typically declines as the gap-time baseline hazard falls.

Instantaneous hazard. The posterior mean hazard at time t is:

$$\hat{h}_i(t | t_s) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M h_i(t | \mathcal{H}_i(t_s), \mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}, u_i^{(m)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(m)})$$

Time to next relapse and relapse count distribution. For each posterior draw m and each inner replicate r , the simulated relapse trajectory yields two quantities: the waiting time from the landmark to the first subsequent relapse, and the total number of relapses within the window.

The predictive distribution of the time to the next relapse is defined conditionally, given that a relapse occurs at all. Within draw m , let $R_{\text{rel}}^{(m)}$ be the number of its R_{inner} replicates that contain at least one relapse, and let $W_i^{(m,r)}$ be the first-relapse waiting time in such a replicate. The conditional cumulative distribution for that draw is

$$G_i^{(m)}(t | t_s) = \frac{1}{R_{\text{rel}}^{(m)}} \sum_{r: \text{relapse occurs}} \mathbf{1}(W_i^{(m,r)} \leq t),$$

that is, the fraction of the draw's relapsing replicates whose first relapse falls within t years of the landmark.

Draws with fewer than ten relapsing replicates are discarded. Such a fraction would rest on only a handful of replicates and be too noisy to interpret. For a low-risk individual in particular, most replicates produce no relapse, leaving little simulated evidence to condition on.

Across the retained draws, the conditional distribution is then summarised by the mean of the per-draw CDFs together with their 95% HDI. This interval reflects genuine between-draw posterior disagreement and widens when relapses are rare.

The relapse count probabilities in the risk profile follow from the same trajectories. For a count threshold k ,

$$P(\geq k \text{ relapses}) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{R_{\text{inner}}} \sum_{r=1}^{R_{\text{inner}}} \mathbf{1}(N_i^{(m,r)}(T) \geq k),$$

the fraction of replicates reaching at least k relapses by the horizon T , averaged over draws. The profile

reports the cases $k = 1$ and $k = 2$, giving $P(\geq 1 \text{ relapse})$ and $P(\geq 2 \text{ relapses})$.

5.4 Threshold Exceedance Probabilities

Several outcomes in the individual risk profile, $P(\text{at least 2 relapses})$, $P(\text{EDSS plus 0.5})$, $P(\text{EDSS plus 1.0})$, $P(\text{EDSS reaching 6})$, T25FW $P(\text{above 125\%})$ and $P(\text{above 150\%})$, and 9HPT $P(\text{above 125\%})$ and $P(\text{above 150\%})$, are derived as the probability that a model-predicted quantity exceeds a clinically meaningful threshold. These thresholds correspond to established, clinically interpretable definitions of disability worsening; for example, EDSS of 6 or higher.

For each posterior draw m , an outcome-specific indicator $J_k^{(m)}$ is evaluated, equal to 1 if the condition for outcome k holds under draw m and 0 otherwise. The corresponding probability is the proportion of draws for which the indicator equals 1:

$$P_k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M J_k^{(m)}$$

For example, for $P(\text{EDSS reaching 6})$, the indicator is

$$J_{\text{EDSS6}}^{(m)} = \mathbf{1}\left(Y_i^{*,\text{EDSS},(m)}(T_{\text{horizon}}) \geq 6.0\right)$$

which equals 1 if the predicted EDSS value, including measurement error, for draw m reaches the threshold at which a walking aid is required, and 0 otherwise. The remaining threshold-exceedance probabilities follow the same construction with outcome-specific indicators and conditions:

- **P(at least 2 relapses):** obtained directly from the relapse simulation as the fraction of inner replicates, averaged over draws, with at least two relapses by the horizon, $P_{\geq 2\text{rel}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{R_{\text{inner}}} \sum_{r=1}^{R_{\text{inner}}} \mathbf{1}(N_i^{(m,r)}(T_{\text{horizon}}) \geq 2)$, where $N_i^{(m,r)}(T_{\text{horizon}})$ is the relapse count in replicate r of draw m . Indicates sustained inflammatory activity.
- **P(EDSS plus 0.5) and P(EDSS plus 1.0):** $J_{\text{EDSS}\delta}^{(m)} = \mathbf{1}\left(\eta_i^{\text{EDSS},(m)}(T_{\text{horizon}}) > \eta_i^{\text{EDSS},(m)}(t_s) + \delta\right)$ for $\delta \in \{0.5, 1.0\}$. Both thresholds are established, clinically meaningful definitions of disability worsening (Lublin et al., 2014). The corresponding EDSS changes $\delta_i^{(m)}(t)$ are also used in the worsening attribution below.
- **T25FW P(above 125%) and P(above 150%):** $J_{\text{T25FW}\rho}^{(m)} = \mathbf{1}\left(Y_i^{*,\text{T25FW},(m)}(T_{\text{horizon}}) > \rho \cdot Y_i^{*,\text{T25FW},(m)}(t_s)\right)$ for $\rho \in \{1.25, 1.50\}$, indicating at least 25% or 50% worsening in ambulation speed.
- **9HPT P(above 125%) and P(above 150%):** analogous to T25FW, applied to the 9-Hole Peg Test, indicating worsening in upper-limb dexterity.

5.5 Worsening Attribution

Background: PIRA and RAW. Disability worsening in RMS can occur either in temporal association with a relapse (Relapse-Associated Worsening, RAW) or independently of any relapse (Progression Independent of Relapse Activity, PIRA). The standard clinical definitions of PIRA and RAW require observing whether a confirmed EDSS increase of sufficient magnitude occurs within a specific time window, and whether a relapse falls within a defined temporal proximity to that increase (Kappos et al., 2020; Lublin et al., 2014).

Distinguishing these two patterns is clinically important because they carry different prognostic and therapeutic implications (Kappos et al., 2020).

Why not directly predict PIRA or RAW? In a prediction setting, both the future EDSS value and the future occurrence of a relapse are uncertain. Directly predicting whether a confirmed disability event will be classified as PIRA or RAW is therefore poorly defined, because the classification itself depends on the stochastic realisation of multiple uncertain future events simultaneously. It is methodologically more tractable and clinically more informative to quantify what share of future worsening, should it occur, is relapse-associated rather than relapse-independent.

Counterfactual attribution via the relapse burden pathway. Rather than relying on a temporal coincidence heuristic, the attribution exploits the structure of the fitted model directly. The EDSS submodel of Section 2 contains the weighted relapse burden term $\beta_2^{\text{EDSS}} W B_{ij}$, which is the explicit pathway by which past relapses raise future EDSS. This term provides a principled counterfactual decomposition of the predicted EDSS worsening into a relapse driven and a relapse independent component.

In dynamic prediction the future relapse times are unknown, so the latent EDSS trajectory is evaluated with the future weighted burden held at zero. This counterfactual trajectory, in which no further relapse contributes to disability, is the relapse independent (PIRA) path; its change from the landmark is

$$\delta_i^{\text{PIRA},(m)}(t) = \eta_i^{\text{EDSS},(m)}(t \mid W B^{\text{fut}} = 0) - \eta_i^{\text{EDSS},(m)}(t_s).$$

The relapse associated contribution is the increment that the simulated future relapse burden adds back through the same fitted pathway,

$$\text{RAW}_i^{(m)}(t) = \beta_2^{\text{EDSS},(m)} \widehat{W B}_i^{\text{fut},(m)}(t),$$

where $\widehat{W B}_i^{\text{fut},(m)}(t)$ is the expected future weighted burden at time t implied by the relapse trajectories simulated under draw m (averaged over the R_{inner} replicates). The total predicted EDSS change is the sum of the two components,

$$\delta_i^{\text{TOT},(m)}(t) = \delta_i^{\text{PIRA},(m)}(t) + \text{RAW}_i^{(m)}(t).$$

The RAW share for draw m is the fraction of the total change carried by the relapse burden pathway, $s_i^{(m)}(t) = \text{RAW}_i^{(m)}(t) / \delta_i^{\text{TOT},(m)}(t)$, defined where the total worsening is positive. The reported RAW share is the posterior mean over draws,

$$P_i^{\text{RAW}}(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M s_i^{(m)}(t),$$

with complementary PIRA share $P_i^{\text{PIRA}}(t) = 1 - P_i^{\text{RAW}}(t)$. The symbol $P_i^{\text{RAW}}(t)$ is kept for continuity with the risk-profile notation, but it denotes a share in $[0, 1]$, not an event probability. Because the decomposition uses the same coefficient β_2^{EDSS} that links relapses to EDSS in the generating model, the RAW share is a genuine counterfactual quantity, the fraction of predicted disability accrual that would not arise in the absence of further relapses, and not merely a measure of relapse density. The RAW share accordingly grows with the prediction horizon. The reason lies in the weighted burden of Section 2: each relapse adds a term that then increases linearly with the time elapsed since that relapse, so the cumulative relapse-attributable contribution ramps up over the window, and steepens as further relapses accumulate. This mirrors the empirical observation

that a higher early relapse load is associated with faster long-term disability accrual (Scalfari et al., 2014). The same decomposition also yields the absolute relapse-associated and relapse-independent EDSS increments, which are reported alongside the share. Uncertainty quantification for the RAW and PIRA shares is addressed below.

Window-relative versus cumulative attribution. The share defined above is window-relative: it is anchored at the landmark t_s , so both increments start at zero and the share describes only the worsening accrued within the prediction window. Because the square-root-time term dominates the latent EDSS trajectory immediately after t_s , the window-relative RAW share necessarily starts near zero and rises as the future relapse burden accumulates. At the baseline landmark $t_s = 0$ there is no relapse history at all, so the share then reflects only the deterministic square-root-time trajectory rather than any individual relapse signal; this baseline case is interpreted with care rather than read as a clinical result. A complementary cumulative attribution removes the reset at each landmark by anchoring the decomposition at first observation. The weighted burden is then built from the observed past relapse times together with the simulated future relapses, $\widehat{WB}_i^{\text{full},(m)}(t) = WB_i^{\text{hist}}(t) + \widehat{WB}_i^{\text{fut},(m)}(t)$. The historical ramp $WB_i^{\text{hist}}(t) = \frac{1}{10} \sum_{t_k^R \leq t_s} (t - t_k^R)$ is the same weighted-burden construction as in Section 2, now applied to the relapses observed before the landmark: each past relapse contributes a term that grows linearly with the time since it occurred, so the historical burden keeps ramping up over the prediction window even when no new relapse occurs.

For the relapse-independent part we exploit a structural property of the longitudinal submodel. The EDSS submodel has a random intercept but no random slope (Section 2). Its relapse-independent component is therefore a fixed function of time plus an individual-specific constant, and that constant is the same at every time point. In any difference between two time points the constant cancels, so the relapse-independent change reduces to

$$\delta_i^{\text{PIRA},(m)}(t) = \beta_{\text{sqrt}}^{(m)} \left(\sqrt{t} - \sqrt{t_s} \right),$$

where $\beta_{\text{sqrt}}^{(m)}$ is the draw- m coefficient of the \sqrt{t} term and t_s is the landmark.

This identity is linear in \sqrt{t} , which has a convenient consequence. Its slope in \sqrt{t} is exactly $\beta_{\text{sqrt}}^{(m)}$, so the coefficient can be read off directly from the post-landmark trajectory and need not be stored separately. The relapse-independent change accrued before the landmark, from the first observation $t_0 = 0$ up to t_s , is then

$$\beta_{\text{sqrt}}^{(m)} \left(\sqrt{t_s} - \sqrt{t_0} \right) = \beta_{\text{sqrt}}^{(m)} \sqrt{t_s}.$$

Adding this pre-landmark offset to the window-relative PIRA increment yields the relapse-independent component cumulated from baseline. As a result, the cumulative RAW share no longer resets to zero at each landmark. Instead it starts above zero whenever the individual already has a relapse history.

5.6 Uncertainty Quantification of the Individual Risk Profile

The uncertainty visualised throughout this document arises from multiple sources that are propagated jointly through the Bayesian framework.

Sources of posterior uncertainty. All predictions are derived from $M = 500$ draws from the fitted MCMC chain. For each draw m , the entire set of model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(m)} = (\beta^{(m)}, \gamma^{(m)}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(m)}, \mathbf{D}^{(m)}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(m)}, \sigma_u^{(m)})$ is taken as a joint sample from the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} \mid \text{data})$. For each draw, individual-specific random effects $\mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}$ and frailty $u_i^{(m)}$ are additionally resampled via the two-phase MH sampler conditioned on the

observed history up to the landmark time, as described above. A predicted outcome trajectory at time t is therefore an M -vector of plausible realisations, one per posterior draw.

How highest density intervals (HDIs) for continuous outcomes are computed. For each prediction time point t , the M predicted clinical outcome values form an empirical distribution of the full posterior predictive distribution. Each draw m contributes a realisation $Y_i^{*(m)}(t) = \eta_i^{(m)}(t) + \varepsilon_i^{(m)}$, where $\eta_i^{(m)}(t) = \mathbf{X}_i(t)\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)} + \mathbf{Z}_i(t)\mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}$ is the latent trajectory and $\varepsilon_i^{(m)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_k^{(m)2})$ is the residual measurement error drawn from the posterior of the outcome-specific residual standard deviation. This ensures that the predictive intervals reflect all sources of uncertainty relevant for a new individual: posterior uncertainty in the fixed effects $\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}$, individual-specific random effect uncertainty $\mathbf{b}_i^{(m)}$ (resampled via the MH sampler conditioned on $\mathcal{H}_i(t_s)$), and measurement error $\sigma_k^{(m)}$. The 95% highest density interval (HDI) is the shortest interval containing 95% of this distribution, computed using the `hdi()` function from the `HDInterval` package. Formally: $\text{HDI}_{0.95}(t) = [l(t), u(t)]$ where $l(t), u(t)$ minimise $u(t) - l(t)$ subject to $\int_{l(t)}^{u(t)} p(Y_i^*(t) | \mathcal{H}_i(t_s)) dY_i^* = 0.95$.

How intervals for the threshold-exceedance probabilities are computed. Each threshold-exceedance probability is itself a posterior quantity: for every draw m it takes a value in $[0, 1]$, and the reported interval is the 95% HDI of these per-draw values across the M draws. It therefore carries the same posterior uncertainty as the continuous outcomes, and not a sampling interval for a single estimated proportion. The per-draw value is formed in one of two ways. For the continuous outcomes, P(EDSS reaching 6) and the T25FW and 9HPT probabilities of exceeding 125% and 150% of the landmark value, the measurement error is integrated out analytically: for draw m the exceedance probability is the Gaussian tail probability $\Phi\left(\frac{\eta_i^{(m)}(t) - c}{\sigma_k^{(m)}}\right)$ of the latent trajectory $\eta_i^{(m)}(t)$ above the threshold c , using the draw-specific residual standard deviation $\sigma_k^{(m)}$ (for T25FW and 9HPT this is evaluated on the log scale, with c the log-transformed threshold). For the relapse counts, P(at least 1 relapse) and P(at least 2 relapses), the per-draw value is the fraction of that draw's R_{inner} replicates reaching the count. A 95% Jeffreys interval $[\text{Beta}(0.025; n_1 + 0.5, n_0 + 0.5), \text{Beta}(0.975; n_1 + 0.5, n_0 + 0.5)]$ on the resulting proportion (n_1 positive and $n_0 = M - n_1$ negative among the M draws) is retained only for quantities that are genuinely binary per draw, namely the confirmed EDSS worsening probabilities P(EDSS plus 0.5) and P(EDSS plus 1.0) and the classification of whether the first confirmed worsening event is RAW or PIRA, where no per-draw continuous probability exists; the Jeffreys interval is well-calibrated for small proportions.

Uncertainty for the RAW and PIRA shares. The RAW share is a deterministic function of each posterior draw: for draw m it is computed from the draw specific future relapse burden and the draw specific latent trajectory. Evaluating it across the M draws yields an empirical distribution of share realisations $s_i^{(m)}(t)$ that already propagates posterior parameter uncertainty, the individual random effects, and the simulated future relapse burden jointly. Its uncertainty is therefore summarised directly by the 95% HDI of this per draw distribution, with no bootstrap and no auxiliary Bernoulli step. The first time point (the landmark itself) is undefined because all EDSS change is zero and is excluded.

Which method applies to which outcome. Collecting the above, the twelve profile outcomes are covered as follows. The posterior mean EDSS (EDSS/10) and the relapse-free survival $S_i(T_{\text{horizon}} | t_s)$ use the pointwise 95% HDI of the posterior predictive distribution over the M draws. P(EDSS reaching 6) and the four T25FW and 9HPT exceedance probabilities use the 95% HDI of the analytic per-draw Gaussian tail probabilities. P(at least 1 relapse) and P(at least 2 relapses) use the 95% HDI of the per-draw replicate fractions. The RAW and PIRA shares use the 95% HDI of the per-draw share distribution. The two confirmed EDSS worsening probabilities P(EDSS plus 0.5) and P(EDSS plus 1.0), which are formed as binary per-draw

indicators, use the 95% Jeffreys interval.

6 External Validation Under Model Misspecification

The parameter recovery analyses in Section 4 establish that the model correctly estimates its own parameters when the data conform exactly to the assumed data-generating process (DGP). A complementary and arguably more clinically relevant question is: *how does predictive performance degrade when the DGP deviates from the fitted model?* This section addresses that question through a systematic external validation study in which a single model, fitted under correct specification of the DGP, is evaluated on validation cohorts generated under three progressively more severe misspecification scenarios, introduced below.

6.1 Validation Framework

6.1.1 Validation Measures

The following metrics are used to characterise predictive performance along three complementary axes. The first axis is accuracy, assessed via the log-score-based R_{\log}^2 and R_{indiv}^2 : these are reported for the overall joint model across all five outcomes, for the four longitudinal outcomes jointly, and separately for each individual outcome. The second axis is calibration, assessed separately for each individual outcome via marginal probability integral transform (PIT) histograms, and jointly for the four longitudinal outcomes via the band-depth rank histogram, which additionally captures their correlation structure. The third axis is discrimination of the recurrent event process within the joint model, assessed via the inverse probability of censoring weighting (IPCW) C-index. This validation framework was developed in this project and extends established approaches from the joint modelling literature (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007; Rizopoulos, 2012; Czado, Gneiting, and Held, 2009; Thorarinsdottir, Scheuerer, and Heinz, 2016; Kim, 2018; Kong, 2025) to the specific setting of multivariate longitudinal outcomes with a gap-time recurrent event process.

Outcome-specific log-score. The negative log-score is strictly proper for arbitrary distributional families (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007): for a probabilistic prediction $g(\cdot)$ and observed outcome Y^* , the negative log-score $SC(g, Y^*) = -\log g(Y^*)$ is uniquely minimised in expectation when g equals the true predictive distribution. Its associated divergence, the Kullback-Leibler divergence, measures how far the predicted distribution lies from the true one. For each of the five outcomes k (EDSS, log-T25FW, log-9HPT, MRI lesion count, and the gap time to the next relapse from the recurrent event process), the per-individual negative log-score at landmark s is

$$SC_{k,i}(s) = -\log g_k(Y_{k,i}^* | \mathcal{H}_i(s), \theta)$$

evaluated at the observed value $Y_{k,i}^*$ of outcome k in the prediction window $(s, s + \Delta t]$, where g_k is the conditional density, or probability mass function for discrete outcomes, of the distribution assumed for outcome k , $\mathcal{H}_i(s)$ is the observed history up to s , and θ denotes the full parameter vector. For the four longitudinal outcomes g_k is conditioned on the random effects b_i , and for the gap-time outcome on the random effects b_i , the frailty u_i and the associations α_k ; the gap-time term combines the hazard and survival contributions and is given in the aggregation below, so that both relapsing and right-censored individuals contribute. The population score for outcome k is the average over the N_s individuals under observation at s and over M posterior draws,

$$SC_k^{\text{full}}(s) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M SC_{k,i}^{(m)}(s)$$

with 95% HDIs from the empirical distribution across draws, propagating parameter, random-effect, and frailty uncertainty.

The null model for the outcome-specific log-score. The raw score $SC_k^{\text{full}}(s)$ is not directly interpretable on its own: its scale and sign depend on the outcome distribution and on the prediction window, making it unsuitable for comparison across outcomes, cohorts, or landmark times. To obtain an interpretable measure, the fitted model is compared, for each outcome separately, against an intercept-only null model that uses only the marginal distribution of that outcome. Formally, the outcome distribution P_k^* has entropy $H(P^*)_k = -\mathbb{E}_{f_k^*}[\log f_k^*]$, and for any null density g the Gibbs inequality states

$$\mathbb{E}_{f_k^*}[-\log g] \geq \mathbb{E}_{f_k^*}[-\log f_k^*] = H(P^*)_k,$$

with equality if and only if $g = f_k^*$. Because the intercept-only null estimates the true marginal as the sample size grows, its expected log-score converges to this lower bound: $SC_k^{\text{null}} \rightarrow H(P^*)_k$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. The marginal entropy $H(P^*)_k$ is therefore the lowest log-score attainable without predictors and the natural baseline against which the fitted model is measured. This per-outcome null serves both as the reference for the two outcome-specific measures defined next and, through the weights SC_k^{null} , in their aggregation across outcomes.

The two outcome-specific R^2 measures. The log-score gain $\Delta SC_k = SC_k^{\text{null}} - SC_k^{\text{full}}$ quantifies how much of the marginal entropy the fitted model resolves through information shared with the predictors. Two normalisations of ΔSC_k are applied, linear and exponential. The linear normalisation is the log-score skill score

$$R_{\log,k}^2(s) = 1 - \frac{SC_k^{\text{full}}(s)}{SC_k^{\text{null}}}$$

which equals 0 at the null, is negative when the model underperforms the null, and is unbounded above, exceeding 1 for sharp continuous predictions whose predictive distribution is substantially sharper than the entropy baseline. Although the Gibbs inequality guarantees that the entropy is a lower bound on the expected null log-score, this lower bound applies only to the *true* data-generating distribution and not to a *fitted* model whose assumed data-generating process may differ from that of the validation cohort. A misspecified fitted model can therefore produce a predictive distribution worse than the null, yielding $R_{\log,k}^2 < 0$; this typically arises when individual-specific random effects sharpen the predictive distribution but centre it in the wrong place, an overconfident yet mislocated prediction being penalised far more heavily by the log-score than the honestly uncertain null. The exponential normalisation, following ideas of Alonso et al. (2016), re-expresses the same gain ΔSC_k as the mutual information between predictions and true outcome on a bounded scale. Their original formulation applies only for $\Delta SC_k \geq 0$; to accommodate the negative values that arise under misspecification, this project extends the transformation symmetrically:

$$R_{\text{indiv},k}^2 = \text{sign}(\Delta SC_k) \cdot (1 - e^{-2|\Delta SC_k|})$$

This quantity lies in $[-1, 1]$ by construction: $+1$ indicates perfect prediction, 0 the null model, and negative values a model worse than the null. The symmetric extension preserves all properties of the original (monotonicity, bounded range, value 0 at the null) while accommodating misspecification, and is a methodological contribution of this project not available in published form. For discrete outcomes such as the Poisson submodel for the MRI lesion count, the upper bound of 1 is not attainable (Alonso et al., 2016); a simulation-based ceiling is therefore estimated under the correctly specified data-generating process and reported alongside the empirical values.

The distinction between the two R^2 formulations. Both measures are normalisations of the same underlying quantity, the log-score gain ΔSC_k relative to the null, and both average over individuals at the same level of aggregation. $R_{\log,k}^2$ normalises ΔSC_k linearly against the null-model entropy, yielding a measure of direct entropy reduction that is unbounded above for sharp continuous distributions ($R_{\log,k}^2 > 1$ is possible and expected for well-calibrated Gaussian outcomes with low residual variance). $R_{\text{indiv},k}^2$ applies an exponential transformation of the same ΔSC_k , expressing it as mutual information on a bounded $[-1, 1]$ scale (Alonso et al., 2016) and is more sensitive to small predictive improvements over the null. The two normalisations are complementary and are both reported.

Bringing the outcomes together: the joint and longitudinal log-score. Beyond the per-outcome measures, the model is evaluated by aggregating across all five outcomes and across the four longitudinal outcomes only. Conditional on the random effects b_i , the frailty u_i and the parameters θ , the longitudinal outcomes and the recurrent event process are independent, so the joint per-individual log-score factorises additively,

$$SC_{\text{joint},i}(s) = \sum_{k=1}^4 SC_{k,i} + SC_{\text{gap},i},$$

where the four longitudinal terms are the conditional log-densities $SC_{k,i} = -\log g_k(Y_{k,i}^* | b_i, \theta)$ and the gap-time term is $SC_{\text{gap},i} = -\log h_{\text{gap}}(W_{i,l+1}^* | b_i, u_i, \alpha_k, \theta) - \log S_{\text{gap}}(W_{i,l+1}^* | b_i, u_i, \alpha_k, \theta)$ when a relapse is observed in $(s, s + \Delta t]$, and $SC_{\text{gap},i} = -\log S_{\text{gap}}(C_i - s | b_i, u_i, \alpha_k, \theta)$ when the individual is right-censored at C_i before the next relapse. Population averaging over the N_s individuals and M draws gives $SC_{\text{joint}}^{\text{full}}(s)$, and the longitudinal score $SC_{\text{long}}^{\text{full}}(s)$ is obtained by restriction to the longitudinal outcome terms. The corresponding skill scores are formed exactly as in the per-outcome case,

$$R_{\log,\text{joint}}^2(s) = 1 - \frac{SC_{\text{joint}}^{\text{full}}(s)}{SC_{\text{joint}}^{\text{null}}}, \quad R_{\log,\text{long}}^2(s) = 1 - \frac{SC_{\text{long}}^{\text{full}}(s)}{SC_{\text{long}}^{\text{null}}},$$

differing from the per-outcome version only in the null against which they are evaluated, specified below.

Bringing the outcomes together: the joint and longitudinal R_{indiv}^2 . For the bounded measure, the aggregation across outcomes is a weighted average of the outcome-specific $R_{\text{indiv},k}^2$ values rather than a transformation of the summed gain. Applying the exponential transformation to the aggregated gain $\sum_k \Delta SC_k$ would saturate the bounded scale and lose resolution, because the exponential approaches its asymptote too quickly once the summed gain is moderately large; weighting the already-bounded per-outcome values avoids this saturation. The longitudinal summary is

$$R_{\text{indiv, long}}^2 = \frac{\sum_{k \in \{\text{EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT}\}} SC_k^{\text{null}} \cdot R_{\text{indiv, } k}^2}{\sum_{k \in \{\text{EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT}\}} SC_k^{\text{null}}}$$

the SC_k^{null} -weighted mean of the outcome-specific $R_{\text{indiv, } k}^2$ over the longitudinal outcomes. The weights SC_k^{null} are the outcome-specific marginal null log-scores: outcomes that are harder to predict (larger SC_k^{null}) receive higher weight, so the summary is not dominated by easily predicted outcomes. The joint summary across all five outcomes, including the recurrent event (gap-time) process, is

$$R_{\text{indiv, joint}}^2 = \frac{\sum_{k \in \{\text{EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT, gap}\}} SC_k^{\text{null}} \cdot R_{\text{indiv, } k}^2}{\sum_{k \in \{\text{EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT, gap}\}} SC_k^{\text{null}}}$$

providing a single comprehensive summary across all outcomes.

Specification of the joint null model. The aggregated log-score measures require a null on the joint scale. A marginal null would treat the outcomes as independent and silently credit the fitted model with reproducing the population-level cross-outcome correlation. To remove this confound, the joint null is itself a fitted joint model with intercept-only fixed effects, the full random-intercept covariance D , and the association parameters between the four longitudinal outcomes and the recurrent event hazard. Its expected negative log-score $SC_{\text{joint}}^{\text{null}}$ thereby estimates the genuine joint entropy of the five-dimensional outcome distribution, which already accounts for the cross-outcome correlation, rather than the sum $\sum_k H(P^*)_k$ of marginal entropies; $SC_{\text{long}}^{\text{null}}$ is obtained from the same fit by restriction to the four longitudinal outcomes. Consequently $R_{\text{log, joint}}^2$ and $R_{\text{log, long}}^2$ isolate the gain from fixed effects and from the dynamic, history-based individual update rather than from reproducing the population-level dependence already present in the null. This correlated joint null is fitted by MCMC under the same machinery as the full model. Two features of the reduced model require weakly informative priors for stable identification. First, the random intercepts of log-T25FW and log-9HPT are strongly correlated (empirically about 0.97), so in the intercept-only null their two association parameters are only weakly separable; a ridge prior (Normal with precision $1/\sigma_\alpha^2$, $\sigma_\alpha = 0.1$) is therefore placed on the T25FW and 9HPT associations, while EDSS and MRI retain effectively flat association priors. Second, the frailty standard deviation is poorly identified in the reduced model and receives a half-Normal(0, 0.5) prior. Convergence is assessed by the Gelman-Rubin statistic and enforced by a differentiated gate: all score-relevant blocks (longitudinal intercepts, residual standard deviations, baseline-hazard spline coefficients, association parameters and frailty standard deviation) must satisfy $\hat{R} < 1.10$, while the random-effects covariance D is held to the more lenient $\hat{R} < 1.50$, since its near-collinear off-diagonal entries sit at the boundary of the positive-definite cone and are intrinsically hard to sample even though their point estimates are stable. If the correlated joint null does not pass this gate, it is discarded and the marginal null is used in its place for $SC_{\text{long}}^{\text{null}}$ and $SC_{\text{joint}}^{\text{null}}$, so that a non-converged null can never silently distort $R_{\text{log, joint}}^2$; in that case the joint R_{log}^2 is reported against the independence-based marginal reference, which is the more conservative baseline.

Dynamic information gain. A key question for dynamic prediction is whether the individual clinical outcome history adds predictive value over and above the population trajectory. In principle, this dynamic information gain can be quantified under either normalisation:

$$\Delta R_{\text{log, dyn}}^2(s) = R_{\text{log, full}}^2 - R_{\text{log, base}}^2$$

$$\Delta R_{\text{indiv,dyn}}^2(s) = R_{\text{indiv,full}}^2 - R_{\text{indiv,base}}^2$$

where the baseline model uses only baseline covariates without incorporating the accumulated longitudinal history; individual random effects and frailty are not updated from the observed history. A value of zero indicates no dynamic benefit from individual outcome histories; positive values confirm that individual trajectories improve predictions beyond what is available from the marginal population model.

Probability integral transform (PIT) histograms. For a continuous outcome with cumulative predictive distribution function F , the PIT value $F(y_{\text{obs}})$ is uniformly distributed on $[0, 1]$ if and only if the predictive distribution is perfectly calibrated (Dawid, 1984). For discrete and mixed outcomes, the non-randomised PIT is used (Czado, Gneiting, and Held, 2009), which avoids the noise introduced by randomisation while preserving uniformity under correct calibration. Deviations from uniformity indicate miscalibration: a \cup -shaped histogram signals underdispersion (predictive intervals too narrow, i.e. overconfident), a \cap -shape overdispersion (predictive intervals too wide), and a skewed histogram systematic bias.

PIT of the observed next gap-time (recurrent event process). For calibration of the recurrent event process, the probability integral transform evaluates the posterior predictive cumulative distribution function of the next gap-time at the individually observed gap-time:

$$u_i^{\text{gap}}(s) = \hat{F}(W_{i,l+1}^* | \mathcal{H}_i(s))$$

where $W_{i,l+1}^*$ is the individually observed next gap-time, i.e. the time to the next relapse, and $\hat{F}(\cdot | \mathcal{H}_i(s))$ is the posterior predictive cumulative distribution function of the next gap-time, averaged over MCMC draws, evaluated at the observed gap-time rather than at a fixed horizon Δt . Because the gap-time formulation resets the time axis after each relapse, the recurrent event process reduces to an ordinary survival waiting time for the next gap, for which the probability integral transform is well defined. Under correct calibration these values are uniform on $[0, 1]$ (Gneiting, Balabdaoui, and Raftery, 2007); for the discrete and mixed components the non-randomized PIT of Czado, Gneiting, and Held (2009) is used. Deviations from uniformity are diagnostic: \cup -shaped histograms indicate overconfident, underdispersed gap-time predictions, inverse- \cup shapes indicate overdispersion, and a systematic skew indicates a directional bias in the predicted relapse timing. Censored individuals are excluded under the assumption of independent censoring conditional on $\mathcal{H}_i(s)$. This measure has no established precedent for the gap-time formulation with individual frailty and constitutes a novel application.

Band-Depth rank histogram. Unlike the marginal PIT histograms, which assess each outcome separately, and unlike the C-index and gap-time PIT below, which apply to the recurrent event process, the band-depth rank histogram assesses the **joint** calibration of the four longitudinal outcomes only (the recurrent event process is not included). To assess this multivariate calibration of the full longitudinal trajectory ensemble simultaneously, including whether the correlation structure among the longitudinal outcomes is correctly captured by \mathbf{D} , the band-depth preranking method of Thorarinsdottir, Scheuerer, and Heinz (2016) is used. For each individual i , the observed d -dimensional trajectory vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_d)$ (one component per longitudinal outcome and prediction time point) is ranked within the M MCMC-predicted trajectories $\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(M)}$ by its band-depth:

$$\rho_{\text{BD}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{k=1}^d \mathbf{1}[x_k \in [\min(x_{i_1k}, x_{i_2k}), \max(x_{i_1k}, x_{i_2k})]]$$

where the average is taken over all pairs (i_1, i_2) from the ensemble. The band-depth prerank measures how centrally the observation sits within the predictive ensemble across all dimensions simultaneously: a high prerank indicates the observation is close to the ensemble centre (high depth), while a low prerank indicates the observation is an outlier relative to the ensemble. If the ensemble is correctly calibrated, these preranks are uniformly distributed over $\{1, \dots, M\}$, yielding a flat rank histogram. Because the band-depth prerank measures centrality rather than a univariate rank, the histogram shape has a specific interpretation that differs from the marginal PIT histograms (Thorarinsdottir, Scheuerer, and Heinz, 2016): a \cup -shaped histogram indicates too little correlation among the longitudinal outcomes relative to the truth, a \cap -shaped histogram indicates too much correlation, a skew toward high ranks indicates overdispersion, and a skew toward low ranks indicates underdispersion or systematic bias. The sensitivity of the \cup/\cap shape to the correlation structure is precisely what makes this diagnostic complementary to the marginal PIT histograms, which cannot detect misspecification of the correlation among outcomes at all.

Population RMSE. For each longitudinal outcome, the population root mean squared error (RMSE)

$$\text{RMSE}_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_s} \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} (\hat{y}_{ik} - y_{ik}^{\text{obs}})^2}$$

measures average point-prediction accuracy at the population level.

C-index for recurrent events. Discrimination is quantified by a count-based concordance index for the recurrent event process. Kim et al. (2018) introduced a global C-index for recurrent event data that compares pairs of individuals by their observed cumulative event counts within a shared follow-up period. Kong (2025) proposed an inverse probability of censoring weighting (IPCW) estimator of the recurrent-event C-index within an Andersen-Gill framework on the counting-process scale, which adjusts for the induced dependent censoring inherent in recurrent events, namely that when earlier events occur the observation window for later events is shortened, creating a dependency between the censoring time and the event history, and which was shown to remain effectively unbiased where the global estimator of Kim degrades under sparse or heavy censoring. Building on the IPCW C-index of Kong, we define a count-based concordance measure adapted to the gap-time formulation with individual frailty by (i) resetting the time axis after each relapse, and (ii) integrating over the frailty u_i in the posterior mean expected relapse count, which serves as the risk score:

$$\hat{C}_{\text{IPCW}}(\Delta t) = \frac{\sum_{i,j} w_{ij} \mathbf{1}(N_i(\Delta t) < N_j(\Delta t)) [\mathbf{1}(\hat{R}_i < \hat{R}_j) + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{1}(\hat{R}_i = \hat{R}_j)]}{\sum_{i,j} w_{ij} \mathbf{1}(N_i(\Delta t) < N_j(\Delta t))}$$

with the pair weight collecting the IPCW correction and the in-window observation requirement,

$$w_{ij} = \hat{G}_i^{-1}(\Delta t | N_i(s)) \hat{G}_j^{-1}(\Delta t | N_j(s)) \mathbf{1}(C_i \geq \Delta t, C_j \geq \Delta t)$$

where $N_i(\Delta t)$ is the observed relapse count for individual i within the prediction window of length Δt , $\hat{R}_i = \hat{E}[N_i(\Delta t) | \mathcal{H}_i(s)] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \text{MCF}_i^{(m)}(\Delta t)$ is the posterior mean expected relapse count conditional on the history up to landmark time s (the mean cumulative function at the horizon, averaged over MCMC draws), and $\hat{G}_i(\Delta t | N_i(s))$ is a stratified Kaplan-Meier estimator of the censoring survival function, stratified by the pre-landmark relapse history $N_i(s)$. A pair contributes only if both individuals remain under observation throughout the window ($C_i, C_j \geq \Delta t$) and differ in their observed in-window relapse counts, with the product weights $\hat{G}_i^{-1} \hat{G}_j^{-1}$ correcting for the resulting selection. Ties in the predicted risk score receive half credit, whereas pairs with identical observed relapse counts carry no true ordering and are non-comparable, hence excluded.

The C-index is a *discrimination* measure for the recurrent event process specifically. It is primarily sensitive to the event submodel (association parameters α and baseline hazard) and largely insensitive to the longitudinal submodels except through the indirect pathway via α . When α_k values are small in magnitude (as for EDSS with $\alpha_1 = 0.05$ and log-T25FW with $\alpha_3 = 0.06$), the longitudinal outcomes contribute little to the C-index. Conversely, MRI with $\alpha_2 = 0.30$ dominates the predicted expected relapse count \hat{R}_i .

6.1.2 Data-Generating Process Scenarios

A single model, fitted under correct specification of the data-generating process, is evaluated on validation cohorts of $n = 500$ individuals generated under four scenarios representing the correctly specified case and three forms of model misspecification, introduced below. Table 6 summarises the key parameter changes and the expected directional effect on each validation measure.

Table 8: Data-generating process scenarios for external validation. DGP-A is the correctly specified reference. DGP-B introduces moderate misspecification of the residual variance and the MRI count distribution. DGP-C introduces severe misspecification including removal of frailty and outcome-relapse associations. DGP-D targets the event submodel by reversing the association parameter signs. All validation cohorts use $n = 500$ individuals.

DGP	Parameter changes	Expected longitudinal effect	Expected discrimination effect
A (correct)	None. Reference scenario.	Reference	Reference
B (moderate)	Residual SDs doubled: $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{EDSS}} = 0.60$, $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{T25FW}} = 0.26$, $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{9HPT}} = 0.14$; time-varying frailty (decay 0.02, corr 0.15 per frailty unit); MRI: Negative Binomial with size = 2 instead of Poisson	$R_{\log}^2 \downarrow$ moderately; PIT underdispersed	C preserved (rank order intact despite miscalibration)
C (strong)	Residual SDs tripled: $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{EDSS}} = 0.90$, $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{T25FW}} = 0.39$, $\sigma_{\varepsilon, \text{9HPT}} = 0.21$; frailty SD $\sigma_u = 0$ (no frailty); all $\alpha_k = 0$ (no outcome-relapse associations); MRI: Negative Binomial with size = 0.2; EDSS plateau effect	$R_{\log}^2 \downarrow\downarrow$; PIT severely underdispersed	C preserved (functional outcomes still rank individuals correctly)
D (event misspec.)	Constant baseline hazard: h_0 -decay = 0; all α_k reversed in sign ($\hat{\alpha}_{\text{EDSS}} = -0.06$, $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{MRI}} = -0.35$, $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{T25FW}} = -0.07$); MRI: Negative Binomial with size = 1	Minimal longitudinal impact	$C \downarrow\downarrow$ (reversed α directly inverts risk ranks)

Three landmark-horizon scenarios are evaluated: $s = 2 \rightarrow T = 5$ years (early landmark, short horizon), $s = 5 \rightarrow T = 8$ years (intermediate), and $s = 7 \rightarrow T = 10$ years (late landmark, maximum training horizon). Together these scenarios assess how performance evolves as more longitudinal history is available to update the individual posterior.

The four DGPs are constructed to deliberately deviate from the fitted model in qualitatively different ways,

with the goal of testing whether the validation metrics respond in the expected direction and magnitude. This is not an attempt to simulate all clinically plausible forms of model misspecification; rather, it constitutes a *sensitivity analysis under known deviations*, following the logic that validation metrics whose behaviour under misspecification cannot be predicted cannot be trusted in practice. Table 6 summarises the key parameter changes, the mechanistic reason for each deviation, and the expected directional effect on each validation measure.

6.2 Overall Model Quality: Log-Score R^2 and Individual R^2

Figure 2: Overall model quality: R_{\log}^2 and R_{indiv}^2 across three landmark-horizon settings. R_{\log}^2 and $R_{\text{indiv,joint}}^2$ are computed jointly across all five outcomes (EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT, and the recurrent event gap-time process); $R_{\text{indiv,long}}^2$ is computed over the four longitudinal outcomes only (EDSS, MRI, T25FW, 9HPT), excluding the recurrent event process. Top panel: R_{\log}^2 (solid bars, unbounded) and $R_{\text{indiv,joint}}^2$ (transparent, bounded in $[-1,1]$) with 95% centred HDI error bars. Bottom panel: $R_{\text{indiv,long}}^2$ (solid) versus $R_{\text{indiv,joint}}^2$ (transparent). DGP-A (blue) = reference; DGP-B (green) = substantial degradation; DGP-C (red) = largest degradation (negative R-squared log); DGP-D (purple) = longitudinal metrics largely intact, degradation concentrated in the event process.

Under the correctly specified DGP-A, $R_{\log, \text{joint}}^2$ lies between 0.82 and 0.85 across the three landmark scenarios, and the $R_{\text{indiv}, \text{joint}}^2$ metric, which is bounded in $[-1, 1]$ by construction, lies consistently above 0.90, together confirming strong individual-level predictive skill when the model matches the data-generating process. Under DGP-B (inflated residual variance and a decaying association structure), both metrics decrease substantially: $R_{\log, \text{joint}}^2$ falls to between 0.27 and 0.40, and the longitudinal contribution $R_{\log, \text{long}}^2$ drops sharply (ranging from 0.16 to 0.35), because the broadened residual variance erodes most of the longitudinal log-score gain relative to the null, while the gap-time component remains comparatively robust. DGP-C shows the largest degradation: with all association parameters set to zero and the frailty variance removed, $R_{\log, \text{joint}}^2$ becomes negative (between -0.47 and -0.28) and $R_{\log, \text{long}}^2$ is strongly negative (between -0.71 and -0.51), meaning the fitted model produces a worse predictive distribution than the correlated joint null for the longitudinal outcomes. Under DGP-D, the event-process misspecification (reversed α and a flat baseline hazard) leaves the longitudinal metrics largely intact, $R_{\text{indiv}, \text{long}}^2$ remains between 0.84 and 0.97, because the reversed association does not distort the outcome trajectories themselves; the degradation under DGP-D is instead concentrated in the event process, as reflected in the lower gap-time and discrimination metrics discussed below.

6.3 Dynamic Information Gain

$\Delta R^2_{\log, \text{dyn}} = R^2_{\log}(\text{full}) - R^2_{\log}(\text{baseline: } b_i=0, u_i=0)$ | Dynamic gain from individual history | 0 = no dynamic benefit

Figure 3: Dynamic information gain $\Delta R^2_{\log, \text{dyn}}$ across three landmark-horizon scenarios. Error bars show 95% centred HDIs.

6.4 Marginal Calibration: PIT Histograms

Landmark scenario: $s=2$, $T=5$ yr | Czado, Gneiting & Held (2009)

Figure 4: PIT histograms: landmark $s=2$, $T=5$ yr. Rows = outcomes, columns = DGP. Uniform = calibrated; cup-shape = underdispersed (overconfident); cap-shape = overdispersed. KS p-value above each panel.

6.4 Marginal Calibration: PIT Histograms

Landmark scenario: $s=5$, $T=8$ yr | Czado, Gneiting & Held (2009)

Figure 5: PIT histograms: landmark $s=5$, $T=8$ yr.

6.4 Marginal Calibration: PIT Histograms

Landmark scenario: $s=7$, $T=10$ yr | Czado, Gneiting & Held (2009)

Figure 6: PIT histograms: landmark $s=7$, $T=10$ yr.

6.5 Ensemble Calibration: Band-Depth Rank Histograms

All Landmark Scenarios | Thorarinsdottir et al. (2016)

Figure 7: Band-Depth rank histograms for all three landmark-horizon scenarios. Each row shows one scenario (top: $s=2$, $T=5$ yr; middle: $s=5$, $T=8$ yr; bottom: $s=7$, $T=10$ yr); each column shows one DGP. A uniform distribution indicates multivariate calibration. High ranks = observation central in ensemble (overdispersed). Low ranks = observation outlying (underdispersed or biased). Chi-squared uniformity test p-value above each panel.

6.6 Population RMSE and Relapse Probability Calibration

Population-level metrics across all DGPs and landmark-horizon scenarios

Figure 8: Population-level validation across all three landmark-horizon scenarios. Top four panels: population RMSE for EDSS, $\log(T25FW)$, $\log(9HPT)$, and MRI lesion count. Bars are grouped by DGP; within each group the three bars correspond to the three landmark scenarios (left to right: $s=2$, $s=5$, $s=7$). The dashed red line marks the null-model standard deviation; bars below indicate the model outperforms a simple mean prediction. Bottom-middle: mean predicted relapse probability versus observed event rate per DGP and landmark scenario; points above the diagonal indicate overestimation. Landmark scenarios are encoded by point shape (square: $s=2$, triangle: $s=5$, diamond: $s=7$).

The population RMSE panels confirm that the fitted model outperforms the intercept-only null for all longitudinal outcomes under DGP-A (bars below the dashed red line). Under DGP-B and DGP-C, RMSE increases proportionally to the inflated residual standard deviation, with DGP-C showing the largest increase, consistent with its $3\times$ residual inflation. DGP-D leaves the EDSS, T25FW, and 9HPT RMSE close to the DGP-A reference, since its misspecification is confined to the event submodel, but the MRI RMSE is markedly elevated (roughly 6.5 to 7.3 versus 2.7 to 3.2 under DGP-A, against a null standard deviation of about 2.0), reflecting the negative-binomial overdispersion introduced in this scenario. The relapse probability calibration scatter plot illustrates a key finding: DGP-B and DGP-C show systematic overestimation (points above the diagonal). This is consistent with the PIT histograms, which show underdispersion under these DGPs: the model predicts with too high certainty, producing predicted probabilities that are systematically too high. DGP-D shows the most erratic deviation because the reversed association parameters systematically mis-rank individuals' predicted risks, a pattern reflected in the lowest C-index values of all scenarios under DGP-D.

6.7 Discrimination: C-Index for Recurrent Events

C-index for Recurrent Events

DGP-B/C: rank order preserved despite PIT underdispersion | DGP-D: reversed alpha breaks rank order

Figure 9: Count-based IPCW C-index for recurrent events across three landmark-horizon scenarios. The C-index quantifies the probability that, among two individuals who differ in their observed in-window relapse counts, the one with more relapses also has the higher predicted expected relapse count: $C = P(\hat{R}_i < \hat{R}_j \mid N_i(\Delta t) < N_j(\Delta t))$, with half credit for ties in \hat{R} . A value of 0.5 indicates random discrimination; 1.0 indicates perfect separation. Shaded bands show 95% centred HDIs. The dashed horizontal line marks the 0.5 reference. Under DGP-B and DGP-C, the C-index remains comparable to DGP-A despite miscalibration visible in the PIT histograms. Under DGP-D, reversed association parameters directly invert the predicted risk ranking, lowering the C-index to the smallest values of all scenarios. Count-based C-index after Kim et al. (2018); IPCW estimator after Kong (2025).

The C-index results illustrate the conceptually important distinction between calibration and discrimination. Under DGP-B and DGP-C, despite substantial miscalibration visible in the PIT histograms (U-shaped,

indicating underdispersion), the C-index remains close to the DGP-A reference (DGP-A: 0.71 to 0.77; DGP-B: 0.73 to 0.74; DGP-C: 0.66 to 0.76). This occurs because miscalibration of the type represented in DGP-B/C affects the absolute scale of predicted relapse counts without necessarily distorting their relative ordering across individuals. The outcome-relapse associations (α) that drive individual risk stratification remain intact in DGP-B and are removed entirely in DGP-C. The C-index is primarily sensitive to the event submodel and responds only indirectly to the longitudinal submodels through the α parameters. Since $\alpha_{\text{EDSS}} = 0.05$ and $\alpha_{\log\text{-T25FW}} = 0.06$ are small in magnitude, these outcomes contribute little to the predicted expected relapse count; MRI, with the largest-magnitude association $\alpha_{\text{MRI}} = 0.30$, dominates the predicted ranking. Under DGP-D, in contrast, the reversed association parameters invert the predicted ranking: individuals who should have high predicted relapse risk receive a low predicted expected relapse count, and vice versa. This is reflected in the lowest C-index values of all scenarios under DGP-D (0.62 to 0.64), confirming that the C-index is uniquely sensitive to event-submodel misspecification of the association structure, whereas the longitudinal metrics are comparatively robust to it.

7 Example of Dynamic Predictions for Representative Individuals

Table 9: Baseline characteristics of the three representative individuals shown throughout Section 7. Risk strata (Low/Medium/High) were defined by a composite risk score combining EDSS, MRI lesion count, age, and disease duration. All clinical outcome values shown are posterior means at the landmark time ($t=2$ yr).

	Risk	Age (yr)	Male	Dis. dur. (yr)	EDSS at landmark	MRI at landmark	T25FW (s)	9HPT (s)
age	Low	54.3	Yes	9.5	2.11	1.18	6.4	23.4
age1	Medium	45.9	Yes	1.0	3.55	1.79	5.7	23.6
age2	High	41.3	No	1.0	5.66	6.17	9.4	27.4

Three simulated individuals from distinct risk strata are shown across three landmark-horizon scenarios: (1) landmark 2 yr, horizon 5 yr; (2) landmark 5 yr, horizon 10 yr; (3) landmark 7 yr, horizon 15 yr. The third scenario demonstrates extrapolation beyond the 10-year training horizon.

7.1 Longitudinal Disease Trajectories

How to read these plots. Each panel shows predicted outcome trajectories for three individuals from different risk strata, from the landmark time through the prediction horizon. The solid line is the posterior mean trajectory: the average predicted value across all $M = 500$ posterior draws. The shaded band is the 95% highest density interval (HDI): the shortest interval containing 95% of the posterior probability mass. Wider bands indicate greater uncertainty, which can arise from heterogeneity in the fixed effects, larger random effect variance, or extrapolation beyond the training data. The three colours represent the Low-risk (green), Medium-risk (orange), and High-risk (red) individuals. Greater separation between the coloured trajectories indicates stronger discriminatory ability of the model.

In the third scenario (landmark 7 yr, horizon 15 yr), the **grey-shaded region** marks the extrapolation zone beyond year 10. The model has not been trained on data from that period, so predictions there rely on the extrapolation of the fitted temporal trends. Uncertainty is expected to be higher in this region, and predictions should be interpreted with appropriate caution.

7.1.1 Landmark 2 yr, Horizon 5 yr

Figure 10: Predicted longitudinal outcome trajectories for the primary scenario (landmark $t=2$ yr, horizon $t=5$ yr). Top row: EDSS trajectory (left) and MRI T2 lesion count (right, count scale after Poisson back-transformation). Bottom row: Timed 25-Foot Walk (left, seconds) and 9-Hole Peg Test (right, seconds). Solid lines are posterior means; shaded regions are 95 percent HDIs. Green = low risk; orange = medium risk; red = high risk.

7.1.2 Landmark 5 yr, Horizon 10 yr

Figure 11: Predicted longitudinal trajectories: landmark $t=5$ yr, horizon $t=10$ yr. A later landmark provides five additional years of observed history, which typically narrows the uncertainty bands compared to the 2 to 5 year scenario.

7.1.3 Landmark 7 yr, Horizon 15 yr (Extrapolation)

Figure 12: Predicted longitudinal trajectories: landmark $t=7$ yr, horizon $t=15$ yr. The grey region marks extrapolation beyond year 10. The model's temporal trends are extended into this region, but the extrapolation relies on parametric assumptions rather than observed data.

7.2 Event Process and Progression Dynamics

How to read the event plots. Six panels characterise the predicted relapse dynamics:

- **Panel A (Relapse-free Survival):** $S(t) = P(\text{no relapse by time } t)$. A value of 0.80 means there is an 80% probability of remaining relapse-free through that time point. Declining curves reflect accumulating relapse risk.
- **Panel B (Expected Cumulative Relapses):** The mean cumulative function $MCF(t)$, the expected number of relapses by time t , obtained from the inner replicate simulation of the gap-time renewal process. Rising curves; higher risk groups accrue more relapses.
- **Panel C (Instantaneous Hazard):** The momentary rate of relapse occurrence $h(t)$ at each time point, derived from the gap-time PWP model. Higher values indicate elevated relapse risk at that moment.
- **Panel D (Time to Next Relapse, conditional):** Among the posterior draws in which a relapse occurs within the horizon, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of when the first relapse occurs. The point estimate is the mean of the per-draw conditional CDF and the shaded band is its 95% HDI across posterior draws, so the band widens when relapses are rare. The dashed line is the unconditional cumulative incidence $1 - S(t)$; the conditional curve lies above it because it excludes draws with no relapse.
- **Panel E (Momentary Relapse Rate):** The instantaneous annualised relapse rate $m(t) = dMCF(t)/dt$, the expected number of relapses per year at each time point. It typically declines as the gap-time baseline hazard falls.
- **Panel F (MRI Lesion Burden):** Expected number of active T2 lesions per assessment, reflecting ongoing inflammatory activity.

All panels show posterior means (solid lines) and 95% HDIs (shaded). Grey shading in extrapolation scenarios marks predictions beyond the training horizon.

How to read the nature-of-progression plots. Five panels characterise how disability accumulates and how it splits into relapse-associated and relapse-independent components:

- **Panel A (EDSS Change with Relapse Probability):** Expected EDSS change from the landmark (left axis, solid), with the cumulative relapse probability superimposed (right axis, dashed). A value on the left axis is the mean predicted worsening in EDSS points; reference lines at +0.5 and +1.0 mark clinically meaningful worsening thresholds, and a trajectory crossing them signals likely confirmed worsening.
- **Panel B (Progression Signature):** Each posterior draw is one point, with the expected number of relapses in the window on the horizontal axis and the total EDSS change on the vertical axis, forming a point cloud per risk group. A cloud rising from left to right indicates predominantly relapse-driven worsening; a flat cloud indicates progression largely independent of relapses.
- **Panel C (Attribution over Time, window-relative):** The RAW share $P_i^{\text{RAW}}(t)$ (solid), the proportion of predicted worsening that is relapse-driven, together with the complementary PIRA share $P_i^{\text{PIRA}}(t) = 1 - P_i^{\text{RAW}}(t)$ (dashed). Both are anchored at the landmark, so the RAW share starts at 0 and the two curves sum to 1 at every time point. At the baseline landmark ($t_s = 0$) there is no relapse history and the share is dominated by the deterministic \sqrt{t} trajectory rather than a clinical signal; such panels are flagged.
- **Panel D (Cumulative Attribution with History):** The same RAW versus PIRA decomposition,

but anchored at first observation rather than at the landmark. The weighted burden now includes the observed past relapses, so the RAW share does not reset to 0 at each landmark; it starts above 0 whenever relapse history is present.

- **Panel E (Weighted Burden Decomposition):** The additive contributions to EDSS change, in EDSS points: the relapse-associated component $dRAW(t)$ (solid) and the relapse-independent component $dPIRA(t)$ (dashed). Their sum is the total predicted EDSS change, so the relative heights show how much of the worsening each mechanism contributes.

Panels A and C to E show posterior means (solid lines) and 95% HDIs (shaded); Panel B shows the per-draw point cloud. The Low-risk (green), Medium-risk (orange), and High-risk (red) individuals are overlaid throughout, and grey shading in extrapolation scenarios marks predictions beyond the training horizon.

7.2.1 Landmark 2 yr, Horizon 5 yr

Figure 13: Event process predictions: landmark $t=2$ yr, horizon $t=5$ yr. See Section 7 preamble for a detailed description of all panels. Green = low risk; orange = medium risk; red = high risk.

Figure 14: Nature of progression: landmark $t=2$ yr, horizon $t=5$ yr. A: EDSS change from landmark (left axis) with cumulative relapse probability (right axis, dashed). B: total EDSS change versus expected relapse count per posterior draw (point cloud). C: window relative RAW share (solid) and complementary PIRA share (dashed), anchored at the landmark; the two curves sum to 1. D: cumulative RAW and PIRA share anchored at first observation, including the observed past relapse burden, so the share does not reset at the landmark. E: additive decomposition of EDSS change into relapse associated $dRAW(t)$ (solid) and relapse independent $dPIRA(t)$ (dashed) in EDSS points. Shading: 95% HDI.

7.2.2 Landmark 5 yr, Horizon 10 yr

Figure 15: Event process predictions: landmark $t=5$ yr, horizon $t=10$ yr.

Figure 16: Nature of progression: landmark $t=5$ yr, horizon $t=10$ yr. Panels as in the $t=2$ to 5 yr figure (A: EDSS change with $P(\text{relapse})$; B: EDSS change vs relapse count; C: window relative RAW vs PIRA share; D: cumulative share with history; E: weighted burden decomposition).

7.2.3 Landmark 7 yr, Horizon 15 yr (Extrapolation)

Figure 17: Event process predictions: landmark $t=7$ yr, horizon $t=15$ yr. Grey region marks extrapolation beyond year 10.

Figure 18: Nature of progression: landmark $t=7$ yr, horizon $t=15$ yr. Panels as in the $t=2$ to 5 yr figure. Grey region marks extrapolation beyond year 10.

7.2.4 Multidimensional Risk Profiles (Radar Plots)

How to read the radar plots. The radar (spider) chart integrates twelve outcome dimensions into a single visualisation. Each axis radiates from the centre (value 0) to the perimeter (value 1). The coloured polygon for each individual is formed by connecting the predicted values on all twelve axes. A larger polygon area indicates a higher overall risk burden across all dimensions.

The twelve axes and their exact meaning are:

1. **P(at least 1 Relapse):** The cumulative incidence $F_i(T_{\text{horizon}} | t_s) = 1 - S_i(T_{\text{horizon}} | t_s)$, the probability of experiencing at least one relapse within the prediction window $(t_s, T_{\text{horizon}}]$.
2. **P(at least 2 Relapses):** Proportion of posterior draws in which the expected relapse count exceeds 2. Indicates sustained inflammatory activity.
3. **P(EDSS +0.5):** Posterior probability that $\eta_i^{\text{EDSS}}(T_{\text{horizon}}) > \eta_i^{\text{EDSS}}(t_s) + 0.5$. Minimal measurable disability worsening.
4. **P(EDSS +1.0):** Same with a threshold of 1.0 EDSS point, representing clinically relevant worsening.
5. **P(EDSS reaching 6):** Probability that predicted EDSS at the horizon reaches 6.0, the threshold at which a walking aid is required.
6. **P(PIRA-driven):** $P_i^{\text{PIRA}}(T_{\text{horizon}})$ from Section 5.5. Probability that future worsening is relapse-independent.
7. **EDSS/10:** Posterior mean EDSS at the prediction horizon divided by 10 (the scale maximum), providing a normalised absolute disability level.
8. **P(RAW-driven):** $P_i^{\text{RAW}}(T_{\text{horizon}})$. Probability that future worsening is relapse-associated. Together with axis 6: $P(\text{RAW}) + P(\text{PIRA}) = 1$.
9. **T25FW P(above 125%):** Probability that walk time at the horizon exceeds 1.25 times its value at the landmark time, indicating at least 25% worsening in ambulation speed.
10. **T25FW P(above 150%):** As above with a 50% worsening threshold, indicating severe ambulatory deterioration.
11. **9HPT P(above 125%):** Same as axis 9 for the 9-Hole Peg Test, indicating at least 25% worsening in upper-limb dexterity.
12. **9HPT P(above 150%):** As above with a 50% threshold.

All twelve axes use the posterior mean as the point estimate. All values lie in $[0, 1]$, making axes directly comparable despite representing fundamentally different clinical quantities.

Risk Profile: Landmark 2 yr -- Horizon 5 yr

Figure 19: Multidimensional risk profile: landmark $t=2$ yr, horizon $t=5$ yr. Each axis shows a posterior mean probability or normalised score on a 0 to 1 scale. A larger enclosed area indicates higher overall risk burden. See Section 7 preamble for a full description of all twelve axes.

Risk Profile: Landmark 5 yr -- Horizon 10 yr

Figure 20: Multidimensional risk profile: landmark t=5 yr, horizon t=10 yr.

Risk Profile: Landmark 7 yr -- Horizon 15 yr (Extrapolation)

Figure 21: Multidimensional risk profile: landmark $t=7$ yr, horizon $t=15$ yr. Grey shading in event panels marks the extrapolation region.

7.3 Uncertainty-Aware Radar Plots

7.3.1 Radar Plots with 95% HDI Bands

Three separate pages are shown: one per risk group (Low/Medium/High), each showing all three prediction scenarios in a 1×3 layout. This allows direct comparison of uncertainty magnitude across risk groups. Larger polygons indicate higher predicted risk; wider gaps between dashed bounds indicate greater uncertainty. Each axis of the radar plot shows the posterior mean (solid thick polygon). The dashed polygons show the upper and lower interval bounds for each axis. The interval drawn on a given axis is the one defined for that outcome in Section 5.6: a posterior 95% HDI for the continuous outcomes (EDSS/10, relapse-free survival), for the analytic exceedance probabilities (P(EDSS reaching 6), T25FW and 9HPT thresholds), for the relapse-count probabilities (P(at least 1 relapse), P(at least 2 relapses)), and for the RAW and PIRA shares; and a 95% Jeffreys interval for the two binary confirmed EDSS worsening probabilities (P(EDSS plus 0.5), P(EDSS plus 1.0)). A wide gap between the dashed bounds on a given axis indicates that the posterior distribution is broad for that outcome dimension, meaning the model is genuinely uncertain about the predicted value. This can arise because the individual has few observations before the landmark, because the outcome itself has high inherent variability, or because the association between outcomes and the event process is weakly identified for that individual.

Figure 22: Uncertainty-aware radar plots for the Low-risk individual across three prediction scenarios. Thick solid polygon: posterior mean. Thin dashed polygons: upper and lower 95 percent HDI bounds. No fill between CI lines. Left: landmark 2 yr, horizon 5 yr. Centre: landmark 5 yr, horizon 10 yr. Right: landmark 7 yr, horizon 15 yr.

Figure 23: Uncertainty-aware radar plots for the Medium-risk individual across three prediction scenarios. Thick solid polygon: posterior mean. Thin dashed polygons: upper and lower 95 percent HDI bounds. No fill between CI lines. Left: landmark 2 yr, horizon 5 yr. Centre: landmark 5 yr, horizon 10 yr. Right: landmark 7 yr, horizon 15 yr.

Figure 24: Uncertainty-aware radar plots for the High-risk individual across three prediction scenarios. Thick solid polygon: posterior mean. Thin dashed polygons: upper and lower 95 percent HDI bounds. No fill between CI lines. Left: landmark 2 yr, horizon 5 yr. Centre: landmark 5 yr, horizon 10 yr. Right: landmark 7 yr, horizon 15 yr.

7.4 Temporal Evolution: Landmark 1–9 yr with Fixed Horizon 10 yr

How to read this plot. Each polygon represents the predicted risk profile for the **Medium-risk** individual at one specific landmark time, with the prediction horizon fixed at 10 years. Nine polygons are shown, one for each landmark year from 1 to 9. The colour ramp transitions from steel blue (earliest landmark, year 1) to dark red (latest landmark, year 9). As the landmark advances, more longitudinal information is available to update the posterior, which typically sharpens the predictions. Changing polygon shapes across landmark years indicate which outcome dimensions are most sensitive to the timing of the prediction.

Temporal Evolution: Medium Risk, Horizon 10 yr

Figure 25: Temporal evolution of the multidimensional risk profile for Medium-risk individuals. Each polygon corresponds to one landmark year (1 to 9 yr), with the horizon fixed at 10 yr. Colour ramp from steel blue (landmark t=1 yr) to dark red (landmark t=9 yr). A shifting polygon shape indicates that the balance of predicted outcomes changes as more longitudinal history becomes available.

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Generated with R Markdown (pdflatex). Analyses performed in R using JMbayer2, HDInterval, fmsb, knitr, and kableExtra.